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Architecture for a Community

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Abstract

Architecture for a Community is an architectural project intent on inspiring a sense of *community* in my hometown, Montpelier, Ohio. Based on the views of several residents who participated in the design process, the village's plan for development, and my own observations, the project looks to utilize the assets of the community to solve the problem of decentralization it faces. The solution developed from these observations is a community recreation center. By providing recreation space for regular use and flexible space to accommodate a wide variety of activities, the building is intended as a place for *community* to be engendered through the regular interaction of its patrons.

This master's thesis in architecture is centered around a building project for the small town of Montpelier, Ohio. Montpelier is a farming community located an hour west of Toledo, and is the town in which I was born and raised. My childhood in this town resulted in a sincere desire to work for positive growth in communities like mine.

The Village of Montpelier lacks a sense of *community* because there is no common, unifying element among groups and individuals save for their geographic closeness. The residents of the town are leaving the community, traveling out of town for recreation and entertainment. As a result, the community has become a group of people that happen to live near to each other but know little about each other. The immediate consequence of all this is a the decreased social and economic activity in the core downtown and historic core of Montpelier.

The community recreation center proposed in this investigation is intended to create a place where members of all walks of life in the village can come and participate in social activities. Indoor recreation is not provided for in the public services of the village, and has been used as a catalyst for positive shifts in the dynamics of many communities.¹ While the community includes several "citizen associations", there are few venues for these groups to meet. By accommodating these elements, a venue for a wide variety of people to come together is created. The building could become a place for regular contact among members of the community.

As an experiment, the process of participatory design was undertaken to further inform the project. By including members of

¹ This trend is demonstrated by the increased emphasis on well-designed community recreation facilities in Cincinnati and New York, a few of which make up the precedents for this project.

the community in the planning, programming and design of the building two results were intended. The first was a more accurate representation of the community, its goals and spatial needs in the building project. The second was to build a level of support for the hypothetical project which would encourage various groups and individuals to talk about the potential for a community-centered project. By its simple implementation, the intention has the opportunity to inspire the sense of *community* by furnishing a subject around which the residents can discuss and plan for the future. This process did elicit a great deal of public discourse about the potential of the project for the village.

The final design is a structure that uses a former high school building to bring people into the historic core of Montpelier. An essential element of the design is the flexible, public space that presents a venue for a wide variety of activities, while providing a permanent and public program for recreation and public engagement. The permanent elements accommodate the regular stimulus for the invigoration of the *community* and the reorientation of the residents toward this common center, rather than out.

Organization: Chapter 1 discusses a definition of *community* based on the readings of several contemporary proponents of the idea. These writers approach the topic from various angles, including historical American communities, sociology, and the economic importance of *community*. This definition leads directly into the description of the community in this investigation, Montpelier, Ohio. This farming village faces a series of problems, not the least of which is a decentralization exacerbated by a vehicular mobility and a lack of a sense of *community* in the central village area.

Chapter 2 describes a process of public awareness and participation in an attempt to develop an architectural project

that fits the community and helps to inspire a sense of *community*. The chapter begins with the definition and explanation of the need, uses and potential results of community participation in a design project. This leads to the development of a methodology for this particular project, its execution and results.

Chapter 3 describes the basis for the project: its intentions, site conditions and building program. This section attempts to draw the diverse elements of the design project into an easily understood foundation. Most importantly, it gives a series of reasons for the choices made in the areas of site and program that are critical to the project.

Finally, chapter 4 describes the design of the building. Several sketches and schematic designs are described in order to provide the process of the design's development. The final proposed building design is described in detail, with great emphasis on the community spaces, their potential uses, and rationale.

I would like to mention a very special thanks to my family: brothers, grandparents, and especially my parents, for their support of this project from the very beginning. Their interest in saving this old landmark and working toward a better community in Montpelier were among the many factors that sparked this idea. My mother's cookies and cider at the public meetings were much appreciated by the participants, and me. I owe a great deal of gratitude to Michelle, for listening patiently through the problems, and for accompanying me on many of those long drives home.

I would also like to thank: Paul Miller of the Leader Enterprise for his sincere interest in the community in Montpelier, and his willingness to cover the public meetings on the front page of his newspaper whenever they occurred; the Village Council for attending my meetings and supporting the idea of a community center; and my committee for supporting this ambitious project.

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As a project intent on reinvigorating a community, it is essential to determine the characteristics that will be addressed. The issues are important not only to rationalize the steps taken but to focus the effort toward a feasible solution. The solution should be one that responds to the myriad of situations and problems that plague a community, the great possibilities/assets inherent in that community, and the ideal of *community* that will hopefully be generated.

This chapter will set the stage for the project by defining these issues. First, the definition of *community* will be discussed as an idea, how communities should operate, and the basic requirements for an effective community according to contemporary writers. The second section discusses several observations about the community including community services, assets, and hurdles and their geographic distribution. This section gives a brief view of the history of the community, its layout, and the institutions that assist in its operation. The urban and building design problems in the community as laid out in the final section of this chapter come primarily from a document prepared for the Village of Montpelier¹.

¹ McKenna (2001). *Village of Montpelier Comprehensive Plan*. McKenna Associates, Inc. July, 2001.

1.1 Definition

1. - A group of people living in the same locality and under the same government.
- The district or locality in which such a group lives.
2. - A group of people having common interests: *the scientific community; the international business community.*
- A group viewed as forming a distinct segment of society: *the gay community; the community of color.*
3. - Similarity or identity: *a community of interests.*
- Sharing, participation, and fellowship.
4. Society as a whole; the public.²

It is important to begin the discussion of the project with a working definition of *community* as it will be applied time and time again in the text and the context of Montpelier. *Community* can refer to a place, a situation, an idea or a group of people. This discussion works toward the development of the intentions of the project.

According to George Carey and Bruce Frohnen, the word *community* comes from two Latin root words. The first, *communis*, means “common” and the second, *communitas*, means “fellowship”.³ From this basic profile, a *community* is a group of people that come together with something in common. There is no limit to where, who, or why. A *community* can be far reaching. According to Carey, the only necessity of a *community* is that the bond be strong enough to encourage fellowship among the members. This fellowship is not necessarily friendship. Miranda Joseph argues that the “common” need not be a positive attribute. It need only be an idea or cause for a group to work for or against⁴.

This “common” usually applies to the place where the members of the purported *community* reside. Their “common”

² *The American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, Fourth Edition* (2000). Houghton Mifflin Company.

³ Carey, George W and Bruce Frohnen, ed (1998). *Community and Tradition: Conservative Perspectives on the American Experience*. New York: Rowan & Littlefield Publishers. p 1.

⁴ Joseph, Miranda (2002). *Against the Romance of Community*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press. Introduction vii.

goal is the maintenance of their society, namely the land they use.⁵ The *community*, then, is made up of a group of people in a specific locale whose goal in living together is the preservation of the society that they have created. An essential feature of this definition is the interaction of these people.⁶ It is inherent in the sociological definition of *community* that the people who work together have face-to-face interaction with each other.

Contemporary theory argues that “the idea of community...is related to the search for belonging in the insecure conditions of modernity.”⁷ Delanty goes on to argue that because of the expanding idea of connectivity, *community* no longer can be narrowly defined in terms of face-to-face contact. Examples of these sorts of communities include the Christian community, the gay-rights community, the pro-choice community.

This broad application requires a further narrowing of the use of “common” in the definition of *community*. Carey and Frohnen, in the introduction to their book, describe these sorts of groups as “interest groups”.⁸ They argue that these organizations are often more interested in advancing their own interests over the “common good”.⁹ This reintroduces an important term for the discussion of *community*. Earlier, a sociological “common” may have related to the locale in which a particular group was residing. This was a definition of that sort of “community”. But Carey and Frohnen argue that a *community* with national, or even international boundaries lack a sense of interest in the good of the local community, related to the historical role of the *community*.

Barry Shain looks to the history of Revolutionary American towns for the basis on which our American sense of *community* is based.

⁵ Wilkinson, Kenneth P (1991). *The Community in Rural America*. New York: Greenwood Press. p 18.

⁶ Ibid. p 2.

⁷ Delanty, Gerard (2003). *Community*. New York: Routledge. p 1.

⁸ Carey, George W and Bruce Frohnen, ed (1998). p 5.

⁹ Ibid. p 6.

He argues that “people must...live together intimately and help each other...achieve a good life.”¹⁰ This good life is achieved through face-to-face interaction with fellow members of one’s community. New England towns of this period were highly dependant on the continuous interaction between the “congregation and township”, meaning the church and the government.¹¹ These communities were highly autonomous and relied heavily on family, religious association and fellow residents, which Russell Kirk called the “indispensable supports of belief and conduct”.¹²

Frohnen goes on to argue (on his own) that these ideas are still important for communities today. Individuals are more productive in stable environments, he argues, and this stability is found through the reliance on involvement in the immediate community in which those individuals reside.¹³ The institutions that make up that immediate community help to establish order and set common standards for the improvement of individuals and the community as a whole.¹⁴ These institutions are working to promote the common good that Carey and Frohnen argued for in an earlier essay.

Kretzman and McKnight call these groups “citizen associations” and recognize them as “the vehicles through which citizens in the U.S. assemble to solve problems, or to share common interests and activities.”¹⁵ For their purpose of individual engagement in the revitalization of a community, the cooperation of these groups is essential. Their assistance is invaluable in promoting the activity

¹⁰ Shain, Barry Alan (1998). "American Community." in Carey and Frohnen (1998). p 40.

¹¹ Ibid. p 44.

¹² Shain quotes Kirk on p 41. From Russell Kirk. "Humane Sociologist: Remembering Robert Nisbet." *University Bookman* 36. (Winter 1996). p 31.

¹³ Frohnen, Bruce (1998). "Commitment and Obligation." in Carey and Frohnen (1998). p 170.

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Kretzmann, John P and John L McKnight (1993). *Building Communities from the Inside Out: A Path Toward Finding and Mobilizing a Community's Assets*. Chicago: ACTA Publications.

because of their direct connection to individuals in the community, and for its continued impact on the community.

In the pursuit of economic development through community participation, Kretzmann and McKnight refer to the assets of a community linked to individuals, associations, and institutions.¹⁶ They recognize that involvement of local association (religious, cultural, athletic, recreational, etc) is very important at the early stages of participation in development.¹⁷ The compilation of the list of organizations can come from several sources, and should be as complete as possible.¹⁸ This ensures that the maximum number of people know are informed of the initiative, and can be included in the discussion.

Jeffrey Hou and Michael Rios refer to this step as “Mobilization” in their case-study of the design of Union Park, Oakland California.¹⁹ In the early planning stages of this park, community groups worked to create a larger network of organizations that were interested in developing the project. Leaders from these groups, and the community, “met several times to brainstorm about effective ways to leverage their resources and political connections.”²⁰ Similarly, staff from the organizing agency actively participated in city-wide forums and met with nonprofit groups to build support for the project. This involvement further extended the initial network of organizations to “a coalition...that was both multisector and multiscalar in nature.”²¹

Miranda Joseph, in an attempt to dispel the romantic myth surrounding the idea of community, proposes that these institutions that are part of a community are important for the economy of the community as well. Building off an idea similar to Delanty's, Joseph

¹⁶ Kretzmann and McKnight (1993). p 6.

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ Hou and Rios (2003). p 22.

²⁰ Ibid. Op cit.

²¹ Ibid.

argues that the organizations that make up a community (non-profits specifically) “offer specific goods not met by capitalism: religion, education, healthcare, arts, social service, social change.”²² Capitalism, comparable to Delanty's “conditions of modernity”²³, offers little in the way of relationships and belonging. The groups that are a part of the community are important for the maintenance of the current American capitalist society by providing what it cannot.

Joseph goes so far as to say that these groups can come to represent the community “metonymically”²⁴: that the nonprofit groups and the community can be referred to interchangeably. “One gives to one's community or to ‘the community’ by contributing labor or money to a nonprofit; nonprofits are asked to represent communities politically, to speak for the communities for which they are metonyms.”²⁵ From Joseph's research, these organizations are an essential part of the maintenance, vitality and improvement of the community of which they are a part.

It can be concluded from these brief references that the *community* is an extremely complex idea, made up of individuals and groups. *Community* can refer to broad or narrowly defined social groups, but related to the group that makes up a small town, the idea of social interaction and the involvement of community groups is essential. Historically, according to Shain, this interaction helped the members of the community to “achieve the good life.” As the members of the *community* interacted, the problems facing an individual could be addressed, and assisted, by the group as a whole. According to Wilkinson, this interaction also helped to maintain the character and integrity of the *community*.

²² Joseph (2002). p 72.

²³ Delanty (2003). p 1.

²⁴ Joseph (2002). p 70.

²⁵ Ibid. op. cit.

A secondary level of interaction is that between the “congregation and township”. The working relationship between the spiritual organizations and the governing body of the community is important to ensure an equitable representation of the beliefs of the community.

For contemporary communities, the “congregation” may not be the representative sector. In this case, the involvement of interest (“non-profit”) groups in the governance of the community is necessary to ensure the equal representation of the people. Acting on behalf of their members, local organizations should be involved in the decision-making process for their community.

Finally, these groups provide more than just representation for their members. As Miranda Joseph discussed, the “non-profits” are essential to the maintenance of a capitalist society. By providing an opportunity for “relationships and belonging”, these groups support the more detached ideal of capitalism.

It seems that in our contemporary social atmosphere, it is important to encourage all of these elements in individual communities as they are found. Individual interaction should be promoted to encourage the involvement of every facet of the community's social structure in daily life. Participation in religious and community groups should be encouraged as a vehicle for individuals to get involved. These groups should then be encouraged to participate in both social and civic venues to ensure the representation of the various members of the community, the maintenance of the standards of the community, and promote a healthy economic atmosphere.

The Village of Montpelier has a great disposition toward "citizen associations" with a variety of religious, civic, social and service organizations that form the core of individual interaction and activism in the community. Because of the small number of residents, 4,320²⁶, much of the membership in these groups overlap.

Religious groups in Montpelier are primarily related to Christian churches. Catholic, protestant and non-denominational churches form the core of the religious life of the community. They include:

- Central United Brethren Church
- First Presbyterian Church
- First United Methodist Church
- House of Prayer
- Montpelier Church of Christ
- Montpelier Church of the Nazarene
- Sacred Heart Catholic Church
- Saint John's Lutheran Church
- Saint Paul's United Methodist Church
- Soul's Harbor
- West Eagle Creek Presbyterian Church
- West Bethesda Presbyterian Church
- Zion Lutheran Church
- Montpelier Ministerial Association

Civic and social organizations are the primary non-ecclesiastic organizations in the community. These primarily promote the interaction of their membership, while usually undertaking a particular fundraising activity annually. These groups usually attach themselves to a particular fund or service organization raising money from the community to assist these initiatives as well as scholarships. These groups include:

- Montpelier Civic League
- Montpelier Area Career Women Association
- Montpelier Rotary
- Montpelier Chamber of Commerce
- Knights of Columbus
- Williams County Historical Society
- Masonic Temple
- Loyal Order of Moose 312
- Fraternal Order of Eagles 2246
- Lake Seneca Property Owners Association
- Montpelier Parent Teacher Association
- Montpelier Vintage Homes Association
- Twice Ten Study Club
- Athena Study Club

²⁶ according to Census 2000, www.census.gov.

Service endeavors are usually associated with the religious organizations in Montpelier. However, a few act autonomously. The two most important of these groups are the Montpelier Public Library and the "See and Do Club". The Library is an independent library with connection to several Ohio library organizations. The Library is funded by the Village. The See and Do Club is funded by various religious organizations and organizes food and clothing for local families and individuals with financial trouble.

Map 1: Village of Montpelier (Population 4,320: Census 2000)
 (Base Map Source: Village of Montpelier)
 05/03

1.2 Montpelier, Ohio

This section provides a brief history of the Village of Montpelier. The brief history is followed by a description of the major elements that give the village its particular character, demonstrating its development and how it took its current urban form. This section does not make any judgment, but merely lays out the facts that are inherent in the village.

The Village of Montpelier is located in Williams County, the northwestern-most county in Ohio. Montpelier began as a village around a saw mill on the St Joseph River.²⁷ The first town plan was devised by Jesse Tucker and J K Bryner in 1845 (fig. 1.1).²⁸

In 1883, the Wabash Railroad finished a connection from Montpelier to Chicago (fig. 1.2).²⁹ This began the railroad boom that made Montpelier a major rail transport depot. The connection from Montpelier to Toledo was completed in 1901, and Wabash Railroad shops and offices were moved there in 1884, 1893, 1908, and 1917. "By 1936, the Wabash employed 400 people in Montpelier." By 1981, the depot was demolished, and the staff had moved to Ft Wayne, Indiana.³⁰

1.1 Detail of early map of Montpelier. Numbered plot represent original town devised by Jesse Tucker and J K Bryner plan. (From *Montpelier, Ohio History 1845-1976*)

1.2 Map of Wabash Railroad connections to Montpelier. (Map from yahoo.com)

²⁷ Miller, Andy (2003). "A Brief History of Montpelier." *Bryan Times*, Thursday, May 8, 2003.

²⁸ Ibid. p 3. Originally from Maynard, Kevin. *A Guide to Williams County's History*.

²⁹ Ibid. p 12. Originally from Whetro, Jecqueelyn. *Montpelier Through the Years, 1845-1995*.

³⁰ Ibid. p 12. Originally from Maynard, Kevin. *A Guide to Williams County's History*.

Montpelier was divided in two by the Wabash (now Norfolk and Southern) Railroad line. The portion of the village "north of the tracks" comprises the historic core of the community. Nearly all of the historic residential stock is located in this area of the village, along with nearly half of the population. This area is characterized by small residential lots, tree lined streets and relatively well-maintained sidewalks. The plat additions that comprise this area date from the mid-nineteenth century and are highly pedestrian friendly. The character of the residential fabric is varied, from small frame cottages to comparably larger brick and stone houses from various periods in the village's history. Most of the houses in the historic core can be dated from the 1870s through the 1920s.

A major element of the core is the Historic Downtown. The downtown is predominantly built on lots from the original town plan (fig. 1.1), south of the historic mill site (Map 1), and remains the civic and perceptual heart of the village. The structures that compose the downtown proper occupy three blocks on both sides of Main Street (see Map 2). Most of these buildings were built before the turn of the twentieth century and feature a variety of Victorian details in stone and metal (fig. 1.5). Village Hall is located adjacent to the downtown, and the majority of churches are located within easy walking distance.

The historic Wabash Depot (fig. 1.7) was located at the south end of Empire Street (Map 1). A small commercial district developed around the depot including several hotels and

1.3,4 Residential selections, small and large (Photos by author)

1.5 Typical Main Street Building Front (Photo by author)

restaurants. The structures that remain in this area are vacant. This location, seven blocks from Main Street, meant that depot traffic likely had little effect on the continued development of the downtown, but the railroad business was certainly responsible for the village's growth from 1883 through the 1950s.

Central in this historic core are the campuses of two of the public school buildings. Built on the site of the original public school building, the elementary school is located on the major north/south axis through the community, Platt Street. The High School is located on Main Street, three blocks to the east of downtown.

Also north of the Norfolk and Southern Railroad, further east on Main Street, is the home of the Williams County Fairgrounds. Host to over 77,000 people for the week of the County Fair in September,³¹ the Fairgrounds is also the site of a variety of activities throughout the year, including several gun, trade and antique shows, auctions, races and concerts. While the number of participants in these activities is undocumented, these activities could easily double the number of people that visit the Fairgrounds every year to nearly 150,000.

Together, the Fairgrounds and Historic Downtown make up the core of the village. However, since the 1970s, the importance of the Historic Downtown has weakened. Beyond the County Fairgrounds, a new commercial district has been developed. This new area includes the village grocery and hardware stores, and is

1.6 Montpelier Village Hall (Photo by author)

1.7 Historic Wabash Depot. (From *Montpelier, Ohio History 1845-1976*)

³¹ According to Gaylene Carpenter, Williams County Fair Board Secretary.

quickly including fast food restaurants, branches of the downtown banks, and other accessory retailers. In addition to spreading west, toward the core, this district is also spreading east.

South of the Norfolk and Southern Railroad, most of the development occurred in the fifties and sixties (Map 1). The streets are laid out in a new grid, off slightly from that of the core. Residential stock is mostly fifties ranch-style houses with a few historic houses slipped into the mix. Most of these streets were developed without sidewalks, seriously deteriorating the pedestrian character found in the historic core.

The municipal park is located along Platt Street south of the Norfolk and Southern. The Park includes the municipal pool, basketball and tennis courts, ball fields and a large picnic structure. The Park wraps around the west and north sides of the high school's existing stadium.

Main Street is the only corridor through the village. Main Street (by State Route 107) connects the village to State Route 15 and State Route 49, which connects the village to nearly all of the communities in the county, and the Ohio Turnpike. Daily traffic counts along Main Street average around 6,100 inside the Village Boundary and 3,000 outside.³² State Route 107 is not a through-highway, so is primarily used by local residents.

The only connection between the north and south portions of the village is the single viaduct at Platt Street. South Platt Street is a section of State Route 576, a north-south through-highway. Traffic counts within the Village Boundary average around 10,500 per day and between 1,400 and 2,500 outside.³³ These indicate a high level of traffic within the community, but less through-traffic than along Main Street.

³² McKenna (2001), Map 4.

³³ Ibid.

1.3 The Problem

In order to effectively improve the community, it is important to address the issues that hinder and even threaten the stability of the community. These issues are drawn in great measure from the *Comprehensive Plan* developed for the Village of Montpelier. They demonstrate the areas of the community that residents feel need to be addressed, with special attention paid to the effective evacuation of the village's historic core, and the lack of community places.

According to the *Comprehensive Plan for Montpelier (2001)*, the top priority for the community is renewal of the historic downtown area.³⁴ As described later, this portion of the Village is recognized by the community as a great asset³⁵, but one that needs a considerable amount of work in order to become a thriving element of the local economy. At present, only about half of the buildings in the downtown are occupied. The occupants vary from insurance sales, barbers, florists, pharmacists, and banks.

One of the primary hinderances for downtown merchants is a lack of incentive for local residents to visit the downtown, compounded by relatively inconvenient parking north of downtown (see Map 2). These issues are exacerbated by the development of a new commercial district approximately 1 mile east of downtown, also along Main Street. This commercial district is quickly incorporating fast food, branches of all of the downtown banks, as well as the community's supermarket and hardware store. These continue to draw customers away from the downtown merchants.

Initial evacuation of the downtown began when the industrial base of the community began building facilities in the new industrial park east of town. While helping to clear the streets of

³⁴ McKenna (2001). p 21.

³⁵ See section 2.3 *What the People Said*, p 39.

forklifts and an excess of traffic and noise, it also destroyed the necessity for much of the population to come to the core of the community on a daily basis. While these moves presented a more pedestrian friendly environment in the downtown and did nothing to injure the economic base of the community, they did hurt many of the downtown service businesses by eliminating much of their daytime customer base.

In addition, the evacuation of the schools from the historic core of the village may encourage the problem of bringing people into the downtown. Currently occupying prime real estate along the major corridors, these facilities drew many parents into the core for school and athletic activities. The current plan is to move all students, grades K-12, to a new facility to be built on land purchased by the board of education. The existing buildings are to be torn down. While the school may not have been a great incentive to stay and patronize the downtown, what help it may have generated will soon be gone.

Also in the Comprehensive Plan, the "lack of a community building" was mentioned as a limitation in the community.³⁶ Many of the other villages in Williams County have invested in what they call "community buildings". In the last several years, the Villages of West Unity, Pioneer, Edon and Edgerton have built these structures which usually consist of a generous banquet-type room (up to 250 occupancy), restrooms, and a small kitchen, usually only suitable for caterers. Ceiling heights of these buildings are usually low (eight to nine feet) and do not have windows. The buildings are usually low, without architectural character. This is probably the type of facility imagined when residents use the term "community building".

The lack of a similar facility is reiterated later in the Comprehensive Plan as a recommendation to "research the

³⁶ *Comprehensive Plan*. Op cit.

feasibility and promote the development of an indoor community recreation building."³⁷ This type of project is needed on several levels the first is to serve the youth in the village. Currently, the public library is the only public building that is capable of filling this need. The facilities, however, have difficulty coping with this use. Immediately following the school day, the public library fills with various ages of young people. The primary intention of these youths is the use of the free internet, but the librarians are commonly referred to as "baby-sitters", making reference to the number of youth that they are responsible for supervising. The result is a public library that doubles (by default) as a youth center. It has become increasingly hard to use the library as such (from my own observation), and in recent weeks police have been called to help the library staff deal with unruly children.

For several decades, the Montpelier High School gymnasium has been used by several groups of citizens for informal basketball games, mornings and evenings. Usually, these groups have included a few of the faculty from the high school who have access to the building, however some are former faculty or staff who have kept a copy of the key to the gymnasium. These activities have become a liability concern for the Board of Education, and the practice was forcibly discontinued. This left a lapse in the athletic opportunities for the community, with only a few outdoor basketball facilities left for recreation. There is only one indoor recreation facility in the county, the Williams County Family YMCA. This facility is open only to members, and is located 15 miles away in the county seat, Bryan.³⁸

In addition to addressing the need for a public facility for recreation, this facility may help to fill the needs of citizen associations in the community by providing meeting space for their

³⁷ Ibid. p 27.

³⁸ See "Williams County YMCA", section 4.0 *Precedents*, p 93.

use. At this time, most groups meet in individual residences, or are forced to meet at facilities outside of the community. Three groups in the village have facilities for their own use, the Loyal Order of Moose, the Fraternal Order of Eagles, and the Montpelier Senior Center. Generally, these groups only permit members to use their facilities. Thus, in order to better connect the true "citizen associations" with each other and the community's interest, a facility for public use should be investigated.

On a much broader scale, the Village lacks a refined space for holding large gatherings (in excess of 100 people). These gatherings could include class reunions, wedding receptions, and, specifically, the "Church Ladies' Luncheon". This gathering of women from the community usually numbers near 400. Currently, the ladies are forced to meet at the Gillette Cultural Arts Center (fig. 1.7) at the County Fairgrounds: a generous pole barn without air conditioning or adequate kitchen facilities.

Similar activities, such as awards ceremonies, memorial services and pageants are usually held in the high school auditorium. This space serves this function well, equipped with a remedial sound system, stage and movable seating. At issue with this facility is a lack of day lighting in the room, air-conditioning, and difficult handicap accessibility. The situation is further compounded by the use of the auditorium for study hall during the school day, the lack of dedicated staff for scheduling and maintenance (currently administered by the high school principal), and the various academic entities that use the facility during the week.

Finally, as the home of the Williams County Fairgrounds, Montpelier is the destination of well over 77,000 visitors every year. Most of these visitors come from other communities within the county, although their point of origin is unknown. At issue is the general lack of connection (through joint or accessory activities and events) that the village exerts on this great opportunity. During

1.8 Gillette Cultural Arts Center, Wms Co Fair (Photo by author)

“Fair Week” (the seven days during which the County Fair is open) the village essentially shuts down. Many residents spend evenings at the Fair, or leave town to avoid it. The community (officially or not) does little to promote itself during this time.

This trend is troubling given the large number of potential investors that travel to Montpelier during “Fair Week” and, as mentioned earlier, over the course of the whole year. It seems reasonable that the village should take advantage of its “destination status” to promote the opportunities available within the community year-round. This may be achieved through some form of permanent presence on or near the fairgrounds for the village's promotion. While this facility should not detract from the Fair, it may lend itself to uses in conjunction with it.

As problems, these conditions present a community without a focus. While the residential core of the village remains, all avenues seem to be looking out, toward the periphery of the village. It seems that in order for any revitalization to take place there must be a reorientation of the community toward the core. This reorientation should be accomplished by way of a permanent, public facility that would regularly encourage the residents of the village to spend time in the core of the village.

2.0 Participatory Design

In order to design for a community, it is important to know as much about the community as possible. The writers discussed in the first section of this chapter demonstrate, from experience, that community participation is important for collecting a broad set of principles about the community, promoting a sense of *community* through mutual interest, and developing more appropriate and sensitive buildings for the community. The second section demonstrates the development of the methodology for finding this information and its execution. The third section discusses the results from these meetings, and its potential application to the project.

2.1 Why Ask the People?

It has been said that a camel was designed by committee, but the camel is an extremely well-adapted animal for its particular environment.

Community Participation is a point of contention for many professions in which it is advocated. All writers, building design, planning or economic who advocate it devote many pages to the defense of the principle of participation in their methodology. Essentially, it is important for the sake of the community, not so much for the designer. While it may prove to lighten the load of the architect in some strange way (perhaps by diminishing the need for public hearings or protests¹), the participation is used to develop a project intended to benefit the people living in a particular area.

The premise of involving the community in this process goes by many names: participatory design, community architecture, etc. This philosophy of empowering the community “grew out of advocacy for the rights of poor and minority citizens.”² In the United States, this movement emerged from the civil rights movement of the 1960s, with young, idealistic professionals working in the inner city to improve conditions there.³ They were inspired by the work of Lucian Kroll, Ralph Erskine, and GianCarlo deCarlo; French, British and Italian architects whose work with cooperative housing was well-published and highly regarded.⁴

Community Architecture in England in the 1980s was thrust into the spotlight when Prince Charles (HRH the Prince of Wales) took it on as a personal cause. The advocates in England sought “to give people a sense of pride and reinforce their identity with their local

¹ As suggested by Michaela Pride-Wells in a discussion about this work. 18 February, 2004.

² Comerio (1987). p 49.

³ Hou and Rios (2003). p 19.

⁴ Ibid.

community.”⁵ They felt that the people who were to use an environment should be involved in its design. This work, they argued, would result in better environments for the community.

There are several reasons for engaging the community in the design of spaces for their use. The first is a practical problem: the design of a successful project for a community requires detailed knowledge of the people and history of that community. This specialized knowledge can be gathered through hours of investigation in libraries and municipal records. An easier way could be to find people who already know this information. “The only people who have [this] ‘expert’ knowledge are the inhabitants-the users.”⁶ By inviting these “experts” of the community to assist in the project at a very early stage, the process of community-specific research can be considerably shortened. This also provides more “relevant and up-to-date information than was possible before.”⁷

Second, successful community improvement is not achieved in a top-down approach. The community needs to be involved for significant growth to occur.⁸ When they are consulted, the members of the community can consider themselves active “contributors to the community-building process.”⁹ This contribution is not to some outside resource, or to the *greater good*, but directly to their quality of life.¹⁰ These projects can also serve to enhance the character of the community. Community participation projects “have served as catalysts to social and economic revitalization in disadvantaged communities.”¹¹ Community participation can “give people a sense of pride and reinforce their identity with their

⁵ Wates and Knevitt (1987), p 17.

⁶ Ibid. p 115.

⁷ Sanoff (1988). p 6.

⁸ Kretzmann and McKnight (1993). p 5.

⁹ Ibid. p 6.

¹⁰ Sanoff (1988). Op. cit.

¹¹ Hou and Rios (2003). p 19.

local community."¹² It can also enhance the sense of participation in a community¹³ because "with a facility as a focus, people willingly negotiate new positions that are mutually acceptable."¹⁴ Even though a project may not be successful, just having worked through the process may be beneficial to the community-at-large.

Third, asking the community for input allows for a greater breadth of knowledge in the use of space. "When people use a facility, they constantly assess its suitability for activities they wish to carry out."¹⁵ Chances are good that no matter what sort of facility or space you are intending to design, some one in the community has seen something similar that, in their opinion, worked or did not.¹⁶ This information will be extremely useful when the time comes to organize a program that the community will eventually use enthusiastically.¹⁷ It is the responsibility of the designer to translate this knowledge, and the basic community knowledge, into physical form.¹⁸

"Some users want and expect to be part of the action" of designing a facility for their use.¹⁹ Participation in the design of a project helps the final users to better understand how design decisions are made, why they are made, and the implications of those decisions.²⁰ This can result in better acceptance of the project after its completion, and a better product for the input of

¹² Wates and Knevitt (1987). Op. cit.

¹³ Ibid. p 115.

¹⁴ Kernohan, David et al (1992). *User Participation in Building Design and Management*. London: Butterworth-Heinemann Ltd. p 5.

¹⁵ Ibid. p 1.

¹⁶ Ibid. p 5.

¹⁷ Sanoff, Henry (2000). *Community Participation Methods in Design and Planning*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. p 10. One reason for community participation is "to provide people with a voice in design and decision making in order to improve plans, decisions, and service delivery."

¹⁸ Hou, Jeffrey and Michael Rios (2003). "Community-Driven Place Making: The Social Practice of Participatory Design in the Making of Union Park." *Journal of Architectural Education*. 57/1, September 2003. p 24.

¹⁹ Kernohan (1992). p 6.

²⁰ Sanoff (2000). Op. cit.

the eventual users. For a facility or place that the community is intended to use, there really can be no doubt that the community should be consulted in its design. If for no other reason than a quicker acceptance of the facility, participation is a must in the design of community space.

So, community involvement in design for their use is important for several reasons: to collect a more thorough base of knowledge, to encourage a sense of *community*, and to design a more appropriate building for the community. The knowledge can assist the architect by demonstrating elements of the community the residents feel are most important, which should then inform the development of the project. The sense of *community* is often developed through the process of participation by providing a common idea around which the residents can gather and discuss. Finally, the completed project (or design) is one that best reflects the needs, wishes and dreams of the community, and one that they would be more likely to accept, support and work enthusiastically to realize.

2.2 Methodology

Public Meetings

The public meeting format was adapted primarily from the case study of the design of the Boulder Creek Branch Library (1985) in Santa Cruz County, California.²¹ In that case, the workshops were developed to inspire creative responses from the participants, including them in activities that both felt like design and would help the professional design process.

Henry Sanoff repeatedly describes this method positively. "Experiences in the participation process show that the main source of user satisfaction is not the degree to which a person's needs have been met, but the feeling of having influenced the decisions."²² In order to maximize this feeling, participants should be allowed to actively work within the stream of design.

The method developed for this project made use of three public meetings. Public meeting 1 was intended to develop a working relationship with the participants, get a feel for the willingness of the community to participate, and collect a base of information on the community. Jeffery Hou and Michael Rios describe this stage of the process as *Discourse Building*. In the case of Union Point Park, the staff of the Unity Council went to great lengths to investigate the desire for open space and other ideas of identity in the community.²³

For the Boulder Creek Library, the first workshop was intended to establish these goals, and "illustrate 'patterns' that describe[d] the 'feeling' that the Library should have."²⁴ These objectives utilized group discussion to develop the requested information.

²¹ Oberdorfer, Jeff (1988). "Community Participation in the Design of a Library." in Sanoff, H ed (1990). *Participatory Design: Theory & Techniques*. Raleigh, NC: Henry Sanoff. p 110-119.

²² Sanoff (2000). p 12.

²³ Hou and Rios (2003). p 22.

²⁴ Oberdorfer (1988). p 111.

Kretzmann and McKnight describe a similar process using a *Capacity Inventory*.²⁵ This survey is intended for use when a member of the development team is interviewing a member of the community. This method protects the anonymity of participant, allowing for general information about resources and capabilities relevant only for individual contribution. This method is difficult to make relevant because of a lack of tangible results for community use.²⁶

The Unity Council approach is highly proactive, going to community groups individually to gain support for the project in addition to gathering information. The Boulder Creek method gathers information from only the most interested members of the community, those who are willing to participate in the design process. The *Capacity Inventory* works only on an individual basis requires a great deal of work, with results that may or may not be relevant to a community-wide project.

The second public meeting was intended to expand beyond the theoretical idea of a community facility, and look to the real issues of site orientation. These issues were to be investigated by the participants through site planning. Jeff Oberdorfer describes this as a "small group decision-making process".²⁷

In the case of the Boulder Creek Library, the architects developed a program from the suggestions made by the participants from the first workshop (similar to Public Meeting 1). This program was then provided to the participants, along with a generic site plan. Participants were asked to consider views, sun orientation, etc as they developed a strategy for placing the building on the site.²⁸

2.1 Postcard sent to community groups for Public Meeting 2

²⁵ Kretzmann and McKnight (1993). p 16.

²⁶ Ibid. p 17.

²⁷ Oberdorfer (1988). p 112.

²⁸ Ibid. p 113.

Public Meeting 3 was intended as a progress report for the community's benefit. The meeting provided a venue for ANY interested party to see the design as it had progressed to that point and make comments toward the feasibility and appropriateness of the project, both in terms of program and design.

In addition to promoting the meeting publicly through the local media, it was important to get feedback for the project from the residents immediately around the community center site. The owners of property on the streets immediately around the site were sent post cards, inviting them to the meeting. They were encouraged to see how the project could affect their neighborhood.

2.2 Postcard sent to owners of property immediately around the site

Special Project Group

With the community invited to participate in the process of design, a large amount of information should be expected. There should be a method in place for interpreting this information and implementing it in a way that the intentions of the community are represented. Nick Wates and Charles Knevitt argue that this implementation is only possible through a “close and creative alliance between experts and users.”²⁹

This can only be accomplished when the expert (the professional/architect...me) is directly accountable to the community. In this case, Wates and Knevitt argue for the creation of what they call a *Special Project Group*.³⁰ This group is created specifically for the purpose of seeing the project through. The members should be a part of the community, and should represent a broad spectrum of the community. Most importantly, this group

²⁹ Wates, Nick and Charles Knevitt (1987). *Community Architecture: How People are Creating Their Own Environments*. London: Penguin Books. p 117.

³⁰ Ibid. p 124.

can act on detail-oriented design decisions throughout the process of design.³¹

In the case of the Union Point Park project, the Unity Council of Oakland implemented much of the community input. The Unity Council had spearheaded the initiative, and retained most of the central control over the project.³² In this capacity, the Unity Council was able to resolve several, potentially debilitating, issues that came up late in the project. One in particular involved a major player in the original plan that threatened to pull out if certain demands were not met. The Council called the bluff, the major player left, the resulting design was far more accessible to the public.³³ This resolution would certainly have been a long, drawn out process had the general public been involved in the discussion.

In many institutional projects that involve community participation, a central committee of the institution retains this authority. In the case of the Seattle Public Library (Rem Koolhaas, 2003) the library's central planning committee controlled the final design decisions.³⁴ With the inclusion of an international, architectural superstar like Koolhaas, a great deal of criticism arose as to the effective implementation of the community's comments into the design.³⁵ It could be argued that the committee was sufficiently disconnected from the community that it did not respond appropriately to the discourse. Conversely, the needs of the library, functionally as well as aesthetically, may have been more important to the committee than some of the smaller ideas presented by the community.

³¹ Ibid. p 141. Wates and Kneivitt argue that the "hard work" is done most effectively with a small number of people with continuity of membership.

³² Hou and Rios (2003). p 25.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Mattern, Shannan (2003). "Just How Public Is the Seattle Public Library?: Pulbicity, Posturing, and Politics in Public Design." *Journal of Architectural Education*. 57/1, September 2003. p. 46.

³⁵ Ibid. p 47.

For the design of the Montpelier Community Center, I elected to invite some of the larger organizations to ask for volunteers to serve on this committee.³⁶ The organizations were asked to provide an individual who would be willing to attend a few meetings a month to resolve the issues addressed by the participants at public meetings. Borrowing from Wates and Knevitt, this group was designated the *Special Project Group*.³⁷ The groups invited were as follows:

- Montpelier Area Chamber of Commerce
- Montpelier Civic League
- Montpelier Area Career Women
- Montpelier Rotary
- Montpelier Senior Center
- Montpelier Area Ministerial Association
- Downtown Montpelier Revitalization Committee
- Montpelier High School (Student)

The response from this invitation was disappointing. Only one group selected a representative for this proposed group over the initial two months of contact. That group, the Chamber of Commerce, selected my father to represent the organization.

This response, as with all the other relatively disappointing results, can most likely be attributed to the academic nature of the project. In order to honestly represent the nature of the project, its academic nature was constantly elaborated. Clearly, a complete lack of certainty in the project that was more than most residents of the community were willing to accommodate.

³⁶ Appendix 5, p 144. Sample letter to SPG organizations.

³⁷ Wates and Knevitt (1987). p 117.

2.3 Inviting the People

At the outset of the project, I felt it was important to contact the local organizations to inform them of the potential of this project. However, there were several “housekeeping” issues that I felt were important to clear up first.

The first public contact for the design of a community center was with the Village Council of Montpelier. As the primary governing body for the village, I felt it essential to publicly announce the invitation of the community to them. My request for time on their agenda was honored³⁸, and I presented the intentions of my thesis on Monday, October 13, 2003.³⁹ The response from the council was very positive.^{40 41}

Following the Village Council meeting, I met with the Board of Education of the Montpelier Exempted Village Schools. The site selected for this project is the existing high school for Montpelier, set to be demolished in the next few years. As rather contentious issue in the community, I felt it necessary to present my intention to advertise the use of the building for my project to the Board. This meeting took place on Tuesday, October 14, 2003.⁴²

The Board of Education was not as excited about the project. Without recognizing or discounting the need of a community center for the community, the Board focused on the unsubstantiated claims of asbestos liability. These claims related to the use of the buildings after the Board had vacated them, and the potential for litigation against the Board in the event of a claim of asbestos poisoning. The Board of Education gave its approval

³⁸ Appendix 1, p 137. Cover letter requesting a place on the agenda of the regular meeting of the Village Council of Montpelier.

³⁹ Appendix 3, p 142. Presentation “Brief”.

⁴⁰ Appendix 13, p 164. Report from the *Bryan Times*, 10.14.03.

⁴¹ Appendix 4, p 143. Summary of conversation by Susan Kannel.

⁴² Appendix 2, p 140. Cover letter requesting a place on the agenda of the regular meeting of the Board of Education.

for the use of the building as the subject of a “purely academic exercise”.⁴³

These avenues cleared, I began the effort to contact local organizations. This effort was intended to bolster public support for the project, and invite the members of these groups to the first public meetings. The list of organizations was collected from several sources, including the website of the Village of Montpelier, phone books and local directories. Important for this exercise was the assurance that the community was not invited as a matter of course. The reason for their invitation was the unique knowledge of the community held by its members. This knowledge is to be utilized in the future design of the community center, and it was for that reason they were invited.⁴⁴

Throughout the public meeting process, a website was maintained for the project. The website was intended to keep provide a permanent presence for the project in the community. By posting results and images of the project on the internet, interested residents could remind themselves of the importance of the topics they participated in, and residents who did not attend meetings could see that progress was being made.

Click [here](#) to connect to the project website.

⁴³ Appendix 15, p 166. Report from the *Leader Enterprise*, 10.15.03.

⁴⁴ Wates and Knevitt (1987).

Public Meetings

The public meetings were designed to involve the maximum number of people in developing the critical ideals of the community center. The goals of the meetings were as follows:

- To gather relevant emotional and physical characteristics that the community (represented by the participants) feel make Montpelier unique.
- To develop a project that represents these qualities and interests of the community, infusing the project with these goals by including the participants in the process of design.
- To improve awareness of the project by word-of-mouth.
- To develop a sense of ownership of the project among participants for having contributed to the project's intentions.
- To evaluate the implementation of these goals.

It was important that the limits of the characteristics and program of the building be developed in a community-driven meeting to allow the participants the feeling of having contributed to the project from the very beginning. This sense of ownership would then press the first three goals. The final evaluation by the community would determine the success of the process. At all times during this process, it is important to maintain a sense of direction and objectives for each meeting.

Public Meeting 1

Attendance for the first public meeting numbered only 13, but the discussion produced several interesting and helpful concepts.⁴⁵ The meeting began with several open-ended questions intended to solicit the qualities of the community the participants felt were important. For the most part, these elements act as individual towers of good in the community. These qualities represent the best that the community has to offer. Any future development must consider these elements as it looks to further improve the community. This future work must investigate methods to use its influence to connect the most relevant of these assets.

The following list represents the positive elements mentioned by the meeting's participants:

- best water (in the world, according to a test...source tbd)
- supportive and Friendly (referring to the people living in the community)
- fairgrounds (County) – brings people to the community
- Williams County Historical Society Museum
- intact downtown
- volunteerism (referring to the people living in the community)
- close to (the Ohio) Turnpike
- large variety of churches
- good parks
- good education system
- good zoning/plan for the future
- good village employees
- good EMS and hospital
- good library
- (people) keep an eye out for each other
- (there are people who have) dreams for a brighter future
- the community is involved in education
- excellent non-profit organizations and service clubs

A brief description of the detrimental trends toward evacuation of the village's downtown followed. This evacuation poses a problem, as it leaves an existing, intact, and historic central element of the community. This presentation raised some interesting discussion about the issues surrounding this orientation of the community to the outside, forgetting its center. More

⁴⁵ Appendix 7, p 148. Public Meeting 1 – Results.

importantly, a later conversation with the mayor and a member of the Village Council in attendance yielded a previous master plan developed by the Council. The trends presented and the village master plan are discussed further in section 1.2 *The Problem*.

The third phase of the meeting focused on an idealized community center. This subject was also left intentionally vague to allow the participants an open range of possibilities. The resultant discussion generated several patterns of use for the new facility. These included patterns for spatial and use types with the qualities of those spaces and the building as a whole.

Space Types

- Kitchen (many uses)
- Raised Space
- Photogenic Areas
- Storage area for tables, chairs
- Adequate restrooms
- Smaller meeting rooms
- Computer Area
- Game room – pool tables, darts, indoor pool
- Daycare
- Teen Hangout
- Playground area
- Study/Reading area
- Lobby with a lounge
- Aerobics classroom
- Recreational Area

Activity Types

- Bean Days Activities (Community's summer festival)
- Banquets
- Graduation/Birthday Party area
- Art Exhibits
- Reverse Raffle
- Family Reunions
- Class Reunions
- Wedding Receptions
- Halloween Judging, Party
- Christmas Party
- Music/Arts

- Village Annual Banquet

Qualities

- Parking
- Handicap Accessible
- Versatile Design
- Sound System
- Well Landscaped
- Acoustics
- Fountain
- Good Location
- "A draw of such beauty that others from the surrounding community come use this facility"
- Historic Aspect – Vintage – looks like Montpelier
- A/C
- Occupancy 300-500
- High ceilings
- Large double doors for vehicles
- Comfortable – not like big city
- Not an industrial look

Questions

- Who does it belong to?
- Who pays insurance?
- Who manages?
- Who cleans? –trash removal-
- What equipment is furnished?
- Cost of rental?

These patterns will be helpful as the program, and eventually the design, unfold by providing a set of filters through which the concepts must pass.

The meeting ended with a brief presentation of the site selected for the project. The site was generally received enthusiastically. Most of the participants were excited about the prospect of an alternative use for a landmark building slated for demolition. Concerns were raised about parking for the new facility (a problem for the current use) and the new, and/or different, traffic that the new use would produce. A recommendation was made to contact the residents directly around the site to determine their stance on the use of the site.

Result

The information gathered from this meeting culminated in the development of the program for the project and the reevaluation of its intentions. The program's development focused on the use and space types suggested by the participants. Many of the qualities suggested by the participants were included in the description of relevant spaces.⁴⁶

At the onset of the project, the intention was the development of a building that would serve a particular need for the community. This was a community center, with the uses to be suggested by the participants at the public meetings. When the assets were compiled and evaluated, three demonstrated potential for inclusion into the greater scope of the project. The first: "excellent non-profit organizations and service clubs" revealed a need for a common meeting place for these very influential parts of the community and its economy.

Two assets presented great potential for impact on the physical make-up of the community. "Fairgrounds" (meaning the Williams County Fairgrounds) brings thousands of people to the

⁴⁶ See section 3.3 *Program*

Village of Montpelier every year. Events include the annual County Fair as well as a host of other events including gun and trade shows, dog shows and even concerts. “Intact downtown” refers to the existing historic commercial buildings that make up the downtown area. The decline of this aspect was discussed at the meeting as a potential hazard for the community, while its very existence was counted as an asset.

At present, these elements are separate, with very little interaction between them. However, the site selected for the project is nearly centered between the two. If done properly, the new building could be seen as a knot, tying the fairgrounds (drawing the people to the community) to the downtown (where commerce has, and could again thrive). It may be possible to draw people, if only a few, to make the trek from the fairgrounds, through the community center, to the downtown.

Focusing only on the community of Montpelier, the community center should be developed as a draw for residents as well. In this case, the intention is to provide services that would bring residents in the community to the central corridor. After they have visited the center, they would be encouraged to keep their business and activities there, especially in the downtown.

Public Meeting 2

In an effort to produce a building that reflects the desires and intentions of the community, the second public meeting asked the participants to make omissions toward the design process. This meeting was designed with two objectives in mind: to further inspire community support in the project and to acquire a basis for planning grounded in the interests of the participants. The attendance was lower for the second meeting, with only 10 members of the public in attendance.

The first objective is hopefully achieved as members of the community are involved in the process, and begin to see how their participation influences the result. To this end, the meeting was designed around the planning of a community center on the site selected. Participants were given a simplified program reflecting the detailed program developed for the project. Their objective was to come to a consensual site strategy in their group. In the end, the two groups developed two different strategies: one saving

2.3 Group 1 Site Strategy saves part of the existing building (black outline) (left)

2.4 Group 2 Site Strategy starts fresh on the site (right)

a portion of the existing building, and the other having cleared the site and starting over.

Besides the use of the existing building, the core ideas of the two strategies are generally the same. Both retain the main entrance orientation to the East. This provides vehicular access from North East Avenue, which has a lower traffic volume than Main Street. While Group 1 used a "Great Hall" method to accommodate both gymnasium and banquet facility, both groups oriented their group meeting spaces toward Main Street. While, according to the groups, this orientation provided the best views from inside, it also allows for a more refined view from the street. The building was also set back from Main Street, allowing for a public park to compliment the building. Madison Street to the North was deemed the "back", where service and parking were to be relegated. When the designs were complete individually, the groups were asked to present their ideas. Both groups were surprised to find the similarities between the two strategies.

These ideas, developed entirely by the participant groups, amount to the accomplishment of the second objective of the meeting: a community-developed basis for planning. The maintenance of East Avenue as the primary entrance, the orientation of views toward Main Street and the parking on Madison Street, and the apparent potential of the existing building seen by one of the two groups are inspiring elements to be considered as the building's design unfolds.

Public Meeting 3

Intended merely as a structured public display of the work so far, the meeting began with a short open house with refreshments provided. By allowing the participants the opportunity to view the models, drawings and sketches, the brief explanation of the design could focus on the ideas, rather than explaining the locations of the various parts of the project. Participants could familiarize themselves with the layout and orientation of the building, before the theory was explained.

During this time, a visitor introduced himself as a neighbor, owning one of the houses across the street from the high school. He expressed great distress at the thought of a proposal to keep the existing building. According to this man, the Board of Education had made an agreement with the property owners in the area that the building would be demolished to prevent an eyesore in their front yards. He was concerned that the Board of Education had gone back on their word. After assurances that the Board of Education was not involved in the process, and explaining that there was a specific use intended for the building, the man was willing to stay for the presentation, and pledged to state his opinions at the end.

The presentation focused on the need for a new community use in the historic core of the community. As discussed earlier, the evacuation of the public schools from the core leaves residents without a public reason for coming into heart of the community. With the revitalization of the downtown as a focus of the community, a use must be found and implemented to fill this gap left by the school.

Given the need for a community use to help reinvigorate the core of the community, the design was presented including program and aesthetics. The response to the program was good, especially the interest in finding providing a use for youth in

community. Most of the participants were ambivalent about the proposed aesthetics. The general consensus of the group was that unless a solid funding base could be found, there was little reason to speculate on what the building should look like. This notion precluded most discussion about the design of the building.

2.5 Proposed Site over aerial photo. Suggested parking annex shown in green. (Aerial courtesy of Williams County Engineer)

The site of the building was deemed appropriate by the group, given its public setting. After financing, the general lack of parking in the area was another major concern. Currently, high school students who drive to school park on the streets around the school. Because the streets are not curbed, cars usually end up in the front yards of the neighbors. This problem was of particular concern to the neighbor in attendance, questioning whether the current situation is suitable for the possible hundreds of visitors that the project could accommodate. With only 28 spaces provided, where would these visitors park?

One solution raised by a participant after the meeting was to purchase the four lots north of the site on East Madison Street (fig. 2.5). This annexation would add more than 100 spaces directly north of the main vehicular entrance, and continue to conceal

them behind the building. This could bring the parking total to nearly 150 spaces which begin to accommodate the large number of people that could potentially use the facility. Of course this addition could be made over a period of time to ensure that the extra parking was necessary.

A concern was raised regarding the past experience with youth-oriented outlets in the community. Apparently, "youth centers" and youth activities have been tried in the village at various times over the last several decades. Each has failed because of a propensity to become "hood hangouts". These activities have included bowling, roller skating, arcades and skate boarding. However, most of these activities have been private endeavors, and were more concerned about making money than providing a service. Additionally, they did not provide either a variety of activities or an organized activity base sufficient to encourage the participation of a variety of youths.

The concerns of financing and parking dominated the meeting. With a resolution to investigate both issues further, the participants voiced their support for the project, and their interest in seeing the idea pressed further. Essentially, so long as the community is inconvenienced as little as possible in the funding

2.6 Schematic Design presentation from Public Meeting 3. (Drawings and sketches by author. Full-size images see appendix __.)

and continued use of the project, there is a general sense of support for whatever design is presented.

On the whole, the participants agreed that a project intended for community use is important for revitalization of the community's core. In general, however, there is little sense of what is the most appropriate project type.

2.4 Conclusions

As a learning experience, the exercise in community participation was extremely valuable. Investigating methods for community engagement, developing my own method, making all the contacts, inviting the groups, preparing for the meetings: all these elements of the process were extremely beneficial, personally.

The involvement of the residents, although few, also helped make the project that much more relevant to the particular community in Montpelier. While most of the elements of the design were the product of research in the programs of other similar projects, it was helpful to prove their inclusion because of requests from participants. It also added weight or importance to certain elements that may not have been as important. For instance, the Game Room may have been included as an element to bring variety to the facility. However, with the discussion of the need for a "teen hangout" and a venue away from the public library, a large space for adolescent recreation was absolutely necessary for this facility.

In the area of the psychological impacts on the community, I believe the results are mixed. First, the participation in the meetings was low. This factor can be traced to two major issues. One issue was a lack of community generation for the project. In this case, the project was of my own creation, and one that was laid at the door step of the community. Rather than slowly build support for the project from the ground up, encouraging individuals and groups to join in the cause, I announced my cause, and set the schedule for its implementation. While the process of community participation may be able to influence the acceptance of the final product, the idea needs to be generated by, or with the help of, the community in order for the process to be truly successful.

This ties directly into the second reason for low participation: the reality of an academic project. Based on the reflections of

conversations from my parents and council members, the community was highly encouraged by the idea, but discouraged by the lack of real concrete potential for the project. This element was unavoidable and would certainly not have been a factor for the project had it been initiated by a group or individual from the community.

On the other hand, based on emails and comments from participants, the impact of the project on the community's discourse was more than successful. Comments from several individuals and groups demonstrate the invigorating potential that a project can have on the way people look at their community. With the high level of publicity the project received, the residents seem to be looking at their community a little differently, and perhaps see more potential in their little town than they thought was there before.

In all, this element of the project was extremely beneficial for me. As a student, the learning experience was invaluable, and helped to bring the various parts of the project together. It also demonstrated the real potential wealth of information that members of the community have, and the resource they contain if appropriately utilized. I truly believe that this process is invaluable when working with a particular community, and intend to use it at every opportunity.

This chapter will discuss the essential elements of the project: its intent, site rationale, and program. These form the core of the solution for the problems discussed earlier.

With the community presented, the intention of the project comes first in the solution. These are drawn from the ideas of community discussed in the first chapter, the ideas and opinions from the public meetings, and the problems and assets inherent in the community. The intentions of the project leads to the selection of elements from particular precedents, both related and unrelated to a community setting.

The site of the Montpelier Community Center is important for its revitalizing potential, its inherent landmark status within the community, and the considerable existing space it presents. With the description of what exists completed, the program for the facility will be discussed. Most important for the program will be the reasons for the inclusion of certain elements.

3.1 Intent

To place to promote community, providing recreation facilities for regular use, meeting space for community engagement and flexible space that can respond to the changing needs of the community using existing context.

The design of this project has several intentions acting as its driving force, to be expressed throughout the design toward a unique expression of the community. These intentions come from the theoretical ideas of *community* and the desired impact it should have on the village. The final product will be a facility promoting a sense of *community* in Montpelier by providing recreational activities for regular use, meeting space for community engagement, and flexible space that can respond to the needs of the community.

Foremost in this project is the desire to promote *community* among the residents of the Village of Montpelier. The idea of *community* is important as a binding factor for the members of the geographic community for mutual help and the stability and definition of the character of the community.¹ According to sociologists, an essential feature of *community* is the direct interaction of the members of the community.² Therefore, in order for *community* to be promoted, a place should be developed where members of the community can regularly interact with each other. Historically, the downtown presented this opportunity, with the shops and activities that required regular visits and, as a result, regular meetings of members of the community.

Because the downtown has declined greatly in the last several decades, it may be necessary to develop a new place for these interactions to be fostered. Based on this assumption, the project will include activities and space for activities that promote these

¹ This idea is derived from the discussions of the theories Barry Shain and Bruce Frohnen from section 1.1 *What is Community?*, p. __.

² Wilkinson, Kenneth P (1991). *The Community in Rural America*. New York: Greenwood Press. p 2.

sorts of interactions. The program will incorporate adequate space for random meetings, as well as the regular meetings of the groups that have, in many cases, become synonymous with the community itself.³ By providing space for these groups, the chances for interaction among members of the community begin to increase. But even more important than these “random meeting places” is the draw that brings residents to this place. The function of this place must be such that residents of all walks and ages come regularly. This factor is absolutely essential to bring people together, and for the project's ultimate success.

The issues described in the problem for the community present a great opportunity for a new kind of project in Montpelier. If planned properly, a project of appropriate scope and intention could tie the great opportunities of the downtown and the fairgrounds together. This project, based on the intention of bringing the community together, may also provide a foundation for stimulus to the village. By providing for the permanent needs of the community (interaction among residents, etc), an infrastructure for the temporal fairground-downtown connection could be developed. The proposed project will be flexibly planned to allow for a variety of events to take place, while at the same time fulfilling specific needs in the community.

An important element of a project of this scope is its site. The facility should be located centrally both for the community and with relation to the desired stimulus. In this case, the desired connection between the County Fairgrounds and the historic downtown should be considered in the selection of the site. It should be located to promote pedestrian access from the major

³ This corresponds with the assertion that many community organizations (non-profits) can come to represent the community that they were created to serve.
Joseph, Miranda (2002). *Against the Romance of Community*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
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should be located to promote pedestrian access from the major areas of the village, as well as vehicular access and convenient parking facilities. These opportunities should be primarily focused on regular use by members of the community, but with additional consideration for access by people from outside the community.

In short, the project will provide a function intended for regular use by residents of the village. The primary intention is to promote a sense of *community* among those who use the facility, and hopefully the village as a whole. Additional consideration should be made for flexible use of the facility by a variety of groups and interests. An intended result, although one which is not entirely possible to predict, is the eventual revitalization of the village core. This revitalization may be accelerated in no small part by the regular draw of residents into the core by this place.

Historic Downtown

Central Business District, and part of original village plan

- has seen a great deal of decline since the 1970s, when "Commercial Addition 2" was added (see Map 1)
- buildings consist of first floor retail/office space and second floor apartments -more than half are vacant top and bottom
- being redeveloped under the auspices of the "Downtown Montpelier Revitalization Committee"**
- with grant money from the State of Ohio, various aesthetic improvements to buildings and infrastructure including street lights, pavement, and interior and exterior renovations of buildings

High School and Public Library

Part of the historic district of Montpelier, and major civic institutions nestled in a historic residential neighborhood

- the High School is slated for demolition in the summer of 2006 when the new K-12 complex is finished on Brown Rd
- the Public Library is consistently overrun by youth after school, inadvertently acting as youth gathering place
- both are major landmarks along the Main Street corridor

Williams County Fairgrounds

Historic location for the County Fair

- for one week in September, the grounds host 77,000 people from around the county, and tri-state area
- is home for the Williams County Historical Society Museum
- the museum is planning several improvements including a building expansion to the south (with more exhibit space) a new memorial park, and increased programming
- the grounds are also host to various trade and craft shows throughout the year
- these include gun shows, dog shows, flea markets, etc

3.2 The Site

The campus of the Montpelier High School presents several opportunities for this project. First, the 50,000 square foot building is soon to be vacated and turned over to the Village of Montpelier. Second, the building is a landmark for the community, architecturally and sentimentally. Finally, the building's location is prominent in and accessible for the community, with a potential for connection between the major elements of Main Street: downtown and the Count Fairgrounds.

These three elements demonstrate a great possibility for maintaining and in fact enhancing an existing community landmark. Given its existing prominence as a destination within the village, the building is in a great position to become a center for the community. This section discusses these issues of significance and site for the existing building and the opportunities that the building presents.

Vacancy and Space

In 2002, the Montpelier Exempted Village Schools were selected to benefit from a State of Ohio program to assist in the construction of new school buildings. The resulting project is a new K-12 school complex that will combine the three buildings that currently make up the school district.

The buildings that are currently used for the high school and elementary school are slated for demolition, with little effort applied to saving, rehabilitating or finding an alternative use for them. The high school currently makes up over 56,000 gross square feet of building. These buildings include a gymnasium, auditorium and over 20 classrooms.

According to the current plan, when the new K-12 complex is complete, the building will be torn down, and the land will transfer deed to the Village of Montpelier. The Village, at this time, intends to develop the land as a community park. In any event, this land is intended to be returned to the community.

Significance

A. Original Building (1915)

In 1913, the public school system was growing rapidly, and the existing building was not proving sufficient. In 1914, The Superintendent of the Montpelier Public School addressed an open letter to the Board of Education and the general public. In the *Semi-Annual Report of the Montpelier Schools, January 26, 1914*¹, Superintendent G. W. Hoffman detailed the overcrowding and general poor conditions of the existing school. The resulting bond issue to build a new school was passed in June of that year².

By this time, the Wabash Railroad had been infusing the community with personnel and resources for nearly 30 years. The staff of the railroad with related services combined with the improving local economy must have made for tremendous growth. This is almost certainly reflected in the growth of the student body of the public school at this time.³

The site selected for the new school had previously been a field, and its relatively new setting within the limits of the town was attributed to the continued and accelerated growth experienced by the community.⁴ The land was purchased from a local landowner in September 1914⁵, and was relatively undeveloped. In the

3.1 Sanborn Fire Insurance Map showing the site in 1910 in red. (From Ohio Public Library Information Network)

3.2 Sanborn Fire Insurance Map showing the site in 1916, building in red. (From Ohio Public Library Information Network)

¹ From *Montpelier Enterprise* (A Free and Untrammled Newspaper), Thursday, February 12, 1914. Vol. XXXIV, p 1.

² From *Montpelier Enterprise*, Thursday, June 19, 1914.

³ Miller (2003).

⁴ From "A High School Site with a History-A Lesson." *Montpelier Enterprise*, Thursday, April 29, 1915.

Enterprise, Thursday, August 12, 1915, the open house for the new building was set for September 13 at which the building was well-received.

By the time requests for "Sealed proposals for the construction of a High School building" were published in July 23, 1914,⁶ the architects for the new high school had already been selected. Thomas Huber of Huber & Gamble, Architects of Toledo, Ohio designed the first building on the site of the high school. The building is designed in a sort of Renaissance Revival Style, featuring a prominent base (water table), shaft (two story body of the building), and capital (cornice).

The building was set facing east, with the main entrance (fig. 3.3) opening onto North East Avenue, a side street. The resulting Main Street elevation is actually the side of the building. While lacking the symmetrical grandeur of the main elevation, this elevation is actually much more interesting, and has acted as the face of the building since its construction.

3.3 Rendering by Thomas Huber. (From *The Mirror*, 1919, Volume I)

3.4 Main Street Elevation. (From *The Mirror*, 1938, Volume XVIII)

⁵ From *Montpelier Enterprise*, Thursday, September 17, 1914.

⁶ From *Montpelier Enterprise*, Thursday, July 30, 1914.

B. Gymnasium Building (1939)

By 1938, the nation had spent nearly a decade in the midst of the Great Depression. In spite of the national dilemma, Montpelier found itself continuing to grow, in no small part by means of the Wabash Railroad.⁷ The continued growth of the community was encouraging greater competition in athletics in the region.⁸ In August of that year, the School district partnered with the Public Works Administration (PWA) to build two new buildings, including a new gymnasium building for the high school.⁹ 1938-1941 was a period of great building programs in Montpelier, funded in major part by the PWA (Public Works Administration). References are made in newspapers of the time to the construction of the high school gymnasium, grade school, water softening plant, post office, and highway garage.¹⁰

The site for the high school addition was annexed from the remaining half of the block.¹¹ The houses on lots 3 and 18 were purchased by the school district and used by the first and second grades while the grade school was built. Classes were in session in these buildings while construction progressed on the gymnasium. The dedication of the gymnasium building was scheduled for November 10, 1939,¹² less than one year from the time bids were requested. With the completion of construction of the grade school in September, 1939, the

3.5 Sanborn Fire Insurance Map (1944) showing gymnasium addition in red. (From Ohio Public Library Information Network)

⁷ Miller (2003). See list of years of Wabash transfers, page 2.

⁸ Darby, Doris. "Building Marks Progress." *The Mirror*, 1939, Volume XIX (Montpelier High School Yearbook). p 2.

⁹ From *Montpelier Enterprise*, Thursday, August 4, 1938.

¹⁰ See Figures 3, 22, 23.

¹¹ See Figure 8.

¹² From *Montpelier Enterprise*, Thursday, November 9, 1939.

houses were relocated to other sites in the area.¹³

In 1941, the United States joined World War II, and patriotism was at a high. The 1941 yearbook decried “The First Defense...Public Schools” with a photo of the new gymnasium building crossing the binding.¹⁴ The community considered their new building a symbol of the training they could provide for the war effort.

The school buildings were designed by Toledo architect Carl C. Britsch. Both reflect a preference toward the refined art deco styling used in most PWA projects. The prominent feature of the relatively unornamented brick box is the entry portal facing Main Street (fig. 3.7). This concrete element acts as the main public entrance for the gymnasium building, as expressed through the period script above the triple entry reading “Gymnasium Building”.

3.6 High School with gymnasium addition. (From *The Mirror*, 1940, Volume XX)

3.7 Gymnasium Entry (Photo by author)

¹³ Interview, op. cit.

¹⁴ From *The Mirror*, 1941, Volume XXI (Montpelier High School Yearbook).

C. Science/Music Wing (1960)

In 1959, the residents of the Village of Montpelier approved a bond issue for additions to the two school buildings in town.¹⁵ The proposed additions came just as the first wave of baby-boomers was entering high school, and the facilities were sorely inadequate. Britsch, [Carl, architect of the gymnasium building,] Mecelwane & Associates of Toledo was employed to design the new additions for both buildings. The high school addition was completed in time for the 1960-61 school year¹⁶, replacing temporary buildings that had been used since 1949.

This portion of the campus reflects the principles of the modern aesthetic. The north façade of the addition is distinguished by stacked ribbons of glazing. These ribbons show no distinction for the rooms within, and are uniformly detailed from end to end.¹⁷ The building features no ornament, a characteristic common among the school additions of the period. The brick matches the existing buildings.

3.8 1960 addition
(Photo by author)

3.9 1960 addition
connection (Photo by
author)

¹⁵ From *Montpelier Enterprise*, Thursday, June 25, 1959.

¹⁶ Notice that each of the three building projects for the high school took less than one year from approval of the bond issue to the dedication of the building.

¹⁷ See Figure 21.

Throughout the history of Montpelier, the construction and expansion of the schools have represented the growth of the community. In 1915, the Wabash Railroad was making Montpelier a hub of rail transportation. Throughout the Depression, the Railroad was pouring money and man-power into the community, resulting in the need to be competitive with other towns in the region. By the 1960s, the stable population base that had come home from World War II were sending their children (the baby-boomers) to high school.

As the students plan to move out of the building, it is important to consider the significance of the building in the contemporary community. As the largest "civilized" meeting facility in the village, the high school auditorium plays host to pageants, musicals, public meetings and the occasional rained out Memorial Day festivities. Groups and organizations (scholastic and not) use the classrooms for their meetings. In these capacities, the high school already acts as a destination for the community and is has a great potential for further and improved use as a community center.

Location

The location of the high school is highly advantageous for a community center. Its location on Main Street and central location in the community make it highly accessible. The site's proximity makes it a potential connection between the County Fairgrounds and downtown.

The high school site is located along the village's main vehicular through-corridor.¹⁸ Located two blocks from the north-south connection for the village, the site is highly accessible by automobile from all points in the village. Geographically, the site is located centrally within the community, and near the heart of the historic residential district. As part of the most walk-able area in the community, this location makes the site highly accessible for pedestrians.

Centered between the County Fairgrounds and Downtown, the site presents an opportunity to connect the major destination in the community, and its historic heart. A public building on this site has an opportunity to provide activities and programs that could draw visitors to the County Fairgrounds into the village, and potentially interest them in the businesses and activities within the community. This proximity is equally helpful for providing incentive for residents to stay in the core and potentially utilize the infrastructure of the downtown. Those who patronize the facility may be more inclined to use the resources more immediately available to them in the downtown than in the other commercial areas.

Across the street from the high school site, the Montpelier Public Library currently provides the only public facility for youth (as described in Section 1.3 *Problem*). This proximity provides an opportunity for a potential programmatic and service connection between the two public facilities.

¹⁸ McKenna (2001)-based on traffic counts by McKenna, Associates.

Finally, located along the major thoroughfare through the community (on the east approach to the County Fairgrounds) the site has a very high visibility. All of the approximately 3,000 people who drive along Main Street see the site. This presents a great opportunity for advertisement (publicized and architectural) for the facility, both to residents and visitors to the village.

The site of the existing Montpelier High School presents a great opportunity for community recreation center. For accessibility, the site is located along the major corridor through the village. For connection, the site presents the opportunity for a link between the County Fairgrounds and the downtown, with the hope of encouraging visitors to patronize the infrastructure of the village. An easy connection is also available by the proximity of the site to the Public Library. Finally, the site is highly visible from Main Street, and presents a great opportunity for architectural and publicized promotion of the facility.

3.3 Program

The program for the Montpelier Community Center reflects the research toward a definition of *community*, the precedents, requests made by the participants in the public meetings, and the constraints of the existing building. In addition to the square footage and design requirements of the spaces, the reasons for the space's inclusion will also be discussed.

The program is divided into two major sections. First, *Recreation Spaces* provide the permanent facilities necessary to encourage regular use of the facility. *Meeting and Gathering Spaces*, provide the flexible space necessary to allow the variety of activities necessary for adequate community involvement. Also important are the administration and service spaces which keep the facility in good working order. Spaces specially requested by the community are highlighted in gray.

1.0 Athletic/Exercise Spaces	13,315 sf	3
2.0 Gathering/Meeting	14,900 sf	11
3.0 Administrative	1000 sf	20
4.0 Service	1,300 sf	24
5.0 Other		24
	30,515 sf	
Circulation (+10%)	3,055 sf	
Total Square Footage=	33,570 sf	

Summary of Spaces

1.1 Gymnasium (Multi-purpose)	6560		2.4 Small Classrooms	2@500	
1.1.1 Equipment Storage	670		2.5 Large Classrooms	3@800	
1.2 Locker/Changing/Restrooms	2@790		2.6 Storage	400	
1.3 Workout/Weight Training	1670		2.7 Restrooms	4@300	
1.4 Game Room	1670				
1.5 Aerobics/Dance	800		3.1 Administrator	200	
1.6 Cleaning/Maintenance	100		3.2 Program Directors	400	
1.7 Vending/Concessions	265		3.3 Reception	200	
2.1 Community Space	±5700				
2.2 Kitchen	600		4.1 Custodial Office	200	
2.3 M/C/A Room	3000		4.2 Janitorial Storage	3@100	
2.3.2 Storage	600		4.3 HVAC	600	

1.0 Athletic/Exercise Spaces

40%

Athletic spaces should be easy to access by the general public. These spaces should be afforded their own, distinguished entry to avoid conflict with formal events in other spaces. Natural light should be an integral part of these spaces. Flexibility should be an essential element for the main athletic space. A convenient control point should be included in the design to ensure an accurate knowledge of the number/ages/groups making use of the facility at any one time. The athletic spaces should be made available during a regular period of time, and events should be able to coincide without interfering with those in the rest of the facility.

Square Footage= **13,315**

1.1 Gymnasium (Multipurpose)

Capacity: variable

Square Footage: 6,560

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
Locker/Changing/Restrooms (1.2)
- Near Connection to:
Administration (3.0)
Vertical Circulation

Spatial Requirements:

- Sized to accommodate (1) full-size high school basketball court [84'x50']
- Sized to accommodate (2) half-courts superimposed and perpendicular to full-size court
- At least ~8' buffer around full court

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Natural Light
 - North facing glass to prevent glare
 - Glass curtain wall, traditional windows, clerestory, skylight
- Open feeling
 - Open structure
 - Glass expanses
- Resilient wood floor
- Acoustics
- Retractable bleachers (comfortable)

Use Types:

- Basketball training
- Pick up games
- Parties
- Fitness classes

Comments:

Uses Gymnasium will primarily be used for recreational activities. The space could be used in an "Open Gym" fashion for general play, or could be used for more organized activities. The space would primarily play host for intramural type indoor athletic activities (basketball, volleyball, etc) throughout the day. The option for division of the court in two should be provided to permit a larger variety of activities. Primary use of the gymnasium will be by the general public.

The gymnasium may also be used for large gatherings of over 200 people. These gatherings could range from banquets to dance activities.

Orientation Natural light should be a major element of the room. Direct sunlight should be obscured to prevent glare. This may be achieved through the use of clerestories or north-facing glass. Views in should allow the casual passerby to observe play in progress, to determine the availability of the courts, and to demonstrate the use of the facility. Views may also allow for community policing of the facility. Views out should allow players the feeling of playing outside. The view may include a line-of-sight to an entrance to allow participants to watch for rides while continuing play. Glazing will need adequate protection/separation from the main space to prevent breaking. This may require guard rails/cages/etc.

Access Access to the gymnasium should be well marked, and open enough to create a feeling of openness and accessibility. No visitor should feel that

they are excluded from the facility. The entrance should also be large enough to allow observation of the activities, both for safety and security. This may require extensive glass at the entrance to allow views in. Exterior walls should be operable to open the space to the outside. These may use overhead, hinged or pivoting media.

Materials The materiality of the gymnasium should reflect the public nature of its use while maintaining a level of refinement conducive to large, formal gatherings. Simple, resilient materials are essential for its maintenance. Light, uniform, colors should prevail, mixing with a light colored wood floor. Color accents may be used to indicate entry/exit, use changes, or design parti.

Design The gymnasium should feel large and spacious. Exposed roof structure painted white, exceeding the minimum height, may add to this effect. Generally, the room should be a large, rectangular open space. This geometry may be modified (by addition) to accommodate the larger building identity and form, but should not be impinged upon. The space should be acoustically treated to deaden excess noise.

Intention This space is necessary for the regular use of the facility by the public. The recreation centers in Cincinnati have found the gymnasiums essential for the continued use of their facilities. As the only gymnasium open to the public, this space could see a considerable amount of throughout the day, but most especially after school. The need for a conditioned space for large events has also been expressed by Village Council members and the general public.

An important element of the all of the gymnasiums of the CRC presented is natural light. Rather than providing a generic, artificially lit box, the CRC gymnasiums introduce natural ambient light to create spaces that are more alive. The introduction of natural light for this gymnasium is essential.

1.1.1 Equipment Storage

Capacity: none

Square Footage: 670

Proximity Requirements:

-Direct Connection to:
Gymnasium (1.1)

Spatial Requirements:

-Securable

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

-none

Use Types:

-Storage of sports/training/safety equipment for athletic facility

1.2 (2) Locker/Changing/Restrooms (Men's and Women's)

Capacity: 50

Square Footage: 790

Proximity Requirements:

- Near Connection to:
Athletic/Exercise Spaces (1.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- Personal storage lockers (small)
- Changing room
- Restroom/shower room

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Natural Light
- Durability
- Serviceability

Use Types:

- Restrooms, changing room, personal effects storage

Fixture Requirements: (OBC 2902.1, No.1, A-3 gymnasium)

- WC -Male **3** 1 per 125 (urinals=no more than 67% WC)
- Female **3** 1 per 65
- Lav -Male/Female **2** 1 per 200
- DF - **1** 1 per 500
- Lockers -Male/Female **50**
- Shower -Male/Female **5** 1 per 10 lockers (AGS 20)
- 1 Service Sink

Comments:

Uses Changing, shower, locker facility, potential use as public restrooms when large activities are accommodated in the gymnasium.

Orientation Locker/Changing rooms should be exposed to natural light. Views out are unimportant. Views in should be completely obscured to allow for privacy.

Access Locker/changing rooms should be directly accessible to the gymnasium with secondary access to administration and other exercise facilities. Changing rooms should have easy access to the main circulation spaces for easy movement throughout the building.

Materials Maintenance and durability should be primary concerns for the Locker/Changing rooms.

Design Arrangement of the Locker/Changing rooms should be primarily concerned with accessibility and easy movement through the space. Arrangement should provide for fluid use of the space when filled to capacity.

Intention In order to properly accommodate the variety of activities that could use the facility, locker rooms are essential. These should be large enough to accommodate a variety of users, and refined enough to accommodate the potential for a large public activity in the gymnasium and community space. Based on criticism by a number of the CRC directors, the locker rooms should be over planned, with more (and larger) lockers as well as more restroom facilities.

1.3 Workout/Weight Training

Capacity: 20

Square Footage: 1,670

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
Locker/Changing/Restrooms (1.2)
- Near Connection to:
Administration (3.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- Sized to accommodate various types of exercise equipment (tbd)

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Natural Light
- Windows for limited views
- Mirror wall
- Impact-absorbant rubber floor

Equipment Requirements:

- tbd

Use Types:

- Personal exercise
- may be performed with trainer

Comments:

Uses Personal exercise, possibly with trainer

Orientation Workout facilities should make use of natural light, but should avoid direct views in from the street. Views out are not essential. The feeling of privacy is preferable.

Access Use of the workout facilities should be limited to adults or children with adult supervision. The entrance should be viewable from the administration area. This space should be very near the locker/changing/restrooms (1.2).

Materials Maintenance and durability should be primary concerns for the workout/weight training space. A mirror wall may be included. Sound insulation is recommended to permit loud music to be played.

Design The workout/weight training space should be arranged with great attention paid to the grouping of related equipment types. The space should be large, generic, and free span.

Intention The workout facilities are intended to promote physical fitness within the community. As with any of the spaces for regular use, a sense of community can be developed between those who regularly use the facilities. Workout facilities must be planned for hard use.

1.4 Game Room

Capacity: 25

Square Footage: 1,670

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
Administration (3.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- Large, generally free-span space

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Simple materials
- Resilient flooring

Equipment Requirements:

- tbd

Use Types:

- Various game activities

Comments:

Uses The game room should include a variety of large and small game activities. These should be arranged in such a way to prevent overlap.

Orientation Natural light with some views are recommended. Game room should be directly viewable by the Administration area (3.0).

Access General access to the game room should be permitted. The entrance should be highly visible, and observation should be highly considered.

Materials Simple, durable, easily maintained materials are a must.

Design An open span, space with high ceilings is acceptable.

Intention The issue of over-crowding in the Public Library has encouraged the investigation of appropriate outlets for the children of the community. Similar spaces in the recreation facilities of the Cincinnati Recreation Commission have proven to be a positive addition. The best of these spaces provide a variety of game activities (video games, pool, ping pong, etc) in an easily observable space. Essential to the success of this space is the variety of activities, feeling of observation while separated enough to allow the children to relax. Equipment should be of a high quality, with special consideration for comfort and flexibility. This space was specifically requested by participants at Public Meeting 1.

1.5 Aerobics/Dance

Capacity: 30

Square Footage: 800

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
Locker/Changing/Restrooms (1.2)
- Near Connection to:
Administration (3.0)
Vertical Circulation

Spatial Requirements:

- large, generally rectangular room

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Natural Light
 - extensive natural light
 - views in should be obscured
 - views out should be limited
- Mirror wall
- Resilient wood floor

Use Types:

- Aerobics
- Dance lessons/rehearsals
- various group aerobic/dance activities

Comments:

Uses Group aerobic/dance type activities

Orientation Views from the street should be eliminated to prevent "peeping". Natural light is recommended. Views out should be limited to prevent the distraction of participants.

Access Aerobics/dance facilities should be easily accessible to the locker/changing/restrooms (1.2). Access should be limited to instructors and staff to prevent unauthorized use.

Materials Only simple colors and materials are necessary in this space. A highly resilient, floating/sprung floor is highly recommended.

Design A single, open space is required.

Intention In an effort to bring a greater variety of activities to the facility, a space intended for dance activities should be provided. Again in the recreation centers of the CRC, these spaces have proven highly beneficial for young and old by allowing individuals with experience to bring a creative outlet for people in the community. Activities in similar spaces of the CRC include dance (jazz, tap, ballet, etc), aerobics, tae kwon do, and various other types. Participants of Public Meeting 1 requested a similar space.

1.6 Cleaning/Maintenance Storage

Capacity: none

Square Footage: 100

Proximity Requirements:

- Near Connection to:
Athletic/Exercise Spaces (1.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- Securable

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- none

Use Types:

- Storage of cleaning/maintenance supplies for athletic/exercise spaces

1.7 Vending/Concessions

Capacity: none

Square Footage: 265

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
Community Space (2.1)
- Near Connection to:
Athletic Spaces (1.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- Securable

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- none

Use Types:

- Distribution of concessions and refreshment to the visitors.

Intention To provide a whole "recreational" or "after school" experience, a space for concessions should be included in the facility. If nothing else, a space for juice/pop/snack machines should be included to maintain a level of self-sufficiency for the facility.

1.8 Other

2.0 Gathering/Meeting Spaces

44%

Gathering/Meeting Spaces are generally reserved for meeting scheduled in advance with the administration of the facility. These spaces should be separated from the Athletic/Exercise Spaces both, visibly and spatially. The entrance to these spaces must be highly public, and grand to convey a higher character. These spaces should be well- and flexibly-lit (naturally and artificially) and ventilated, with relatively high ceilings. These spaces should have an individual character to give the occupant/user the sense of a unique environment, not a generic room for meetings.

Square Footage= **14,900**

2.1 Community Space

Capacity: n/a

Square Footage: ±5700

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct connection to:
 - Administration (3.0)
 - Vertical Circulation
 - Main entrance
- Near connection to:
 - Main vertical circulation
- Separation from:
 - Athletic/Exercise Spaces (2.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- High ceilings
- multi-story space
- Natural light
- Central, organizing space
- Part of entry sequence
- Provides views from other spaces

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Bright
- lots of light – natural and artificial
- Entry feel
- grand-entry materials
- Organizing philosophy
- reflects the design intentions of the addition
- ties the new with the old

Use Types:

- Gathering
 - small and medium group gathering
- Photo-opportunities
- Queuing
 - waiting for doors to open
- Reception
 - Coat Check
 - Check invitations
 - Monitor entrance

Comments:

Uses The “Community Space” will act as the main reception space for the building, circulation core, and flexible space for parties, gatherings, etc. This space is intended for informal gathering and chance meetings.

Orientation The “Community Space” should act as the spatial and orientation core for the complex. It should be easily accessible (physically or visibly) from all major spaces in the building. Natural light should be incorporated, with a preference for indirect light.

Access The “Community Space” should be directly accessible to all public entry points. It should also relate directly (or nearly directly) to all public circulation and public spaces. Access from the Athletic/Exercise Spaces may be flexible to allow for formal use of the space with related to the.

Materials The “Community Space” should be clean and bright. Light, neutral colors should allow for the visual meeting of multiple spaces. Materials should accommodate the flexibility inherent in its orientation both

toward the exterior spaces and the gymnasium. These connections should be considered to accommodate foot traffic, weather changes, and waiting.

Design The "Hub" should not only be the physical/visual center of the building, but should act as the lynch pin for the design of the whole building. While it need not exhibit the whole of the parti in its design, the space should reflect a great deal of the design intentions of the facility. Material and color may be drawn from other parts of the building and fit into the space. In any case, the "Hub" should not feel like a left-over space, but a unique and spatially complete element of the facility.

Intention An essential part of creating a sense of *community* is providing adequate space for informal gathering. In a facility that brings together multiple groups and activities, it is important that these groups have the opportunity to meet and see each other. To provide a grand space for circulation puts all groups at the same basic level, and prevents hierarchy within the building. This space is also intended for potential formal events. A smooth connection between the gymnasium and community space would provide a very large series of spaces that could accommodate a large number of people. Direct connections to the outside would provide further opportunities for flexible events.

The community space in the College Hill Recreation Center provides a similar use. This gives the facility a much more open feeling, and makes for much less directional circulation. The corridors of the other facilities do not provide this communal feeling.

2.2 Kitchen

Capacity: 10

Square Footage: 600

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct connection to:
Vertical Circulation
- Near connection to:
Meeting/Conference/Activity Room (2.3)
Gymnasium (1.1)

Spatial Requirements:

- Space for minor food preparation
- Serve mostly as warming kitchen for caterers
 - lots of counter space
- Serving window for passing/buffets
- “In” and “out” doors for servers
- Natural Light
- Service access for events/equipment
- Direct exhaust
- Variable climate control

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Bright
- Servicable
 - surfaces washable with hose

Use Types:

- Food preparation
- Catering warming

Comments:

Uses The Kitchen will be used primarily for the warming of catered food. The Kitchen may be used for the preparation of food. This requires the accommodation some cooking appliances, but mostly for counter and “assembly” spaces for caterers.

Orientation The Kitchen should have a clear connection between both the Meeting/Conference/Activity Room (2.3) and Gymnasium (1.1). Natural light would be preferable.

Access Entrance from the central circulation space should be provided. The Kitchen should have a mechanical connection to the main floor and the Meeting floor, probably in the form of a dumb waiter.

Materials Easy maintenance should be the primary intention in the material selection for the Kitchen. Easy cleanup should be planned.

Design The Kitchen should be designed for the easy flow of servers through the space. Easy assembly of catered items should also be intended in the layout of the Kitchen.

Intentions A well-appointed kitchen is needed for a successfully catered event. This attribute was also requested by participants at Public Meeting 1. Ms Alrichs praised the accessibility of the kitchen of the Corryville Recreation Center, as well as the inclusion of “commercial grade” appliances. This allows for larger uses, easier cleanup, and more resilient equipment.

2.3 Meeting/Conference/Activity Room

Capacity: 200(lecture style) or 25x3(divided spaces)

Square Footage: 3000

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct connection to:
 - Vertical Circulation
- Near Connection to:
 - Restrooms (1.4)
- Separation from:
 - Athletic/Exercise Spaces (2.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- Sound isolation
- High ceilings
- Views
- Flexibility
 - potential for breaking space into smaller areas
- Hard floors
- Break-out spaces
 - spatially separated areas for small group discussion

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Bright
- Durability
 - allow for soft to medium uses
 - soft use – group/organization meetings
 - medium use – dance/music rehearsal
- Natural Light (flexible)
 - Large windows
 - controls to block out natural light when deemed appropriate
- Flexibility
 - easy to arrange for various activities
 - relatively uniform treatment throughout

Use Types:

- Organization meetings
- Music rehearsals
- Dance rehearsals

Comments:

Uses The Meeting/Conference/Activity Room may be used for large group meetings, smaller break-down size groups, or group activities such as crafts, dance lessons, or music rehearsals.

Orientation The M/C/A should have extensive access to natural light. Views should not include high traffic areas to prevent distraction of occupants. Views in should be limited to allow for the privacy of occupants.

Access The M/C/A should be accessible from the main circulation areas, but need not be directly accessible from any other part of the facility. This allows for separation of activities within the facility, while providing easy access to this secondary element.

Materials Because of the variety of uses proposed, materials should be resilient to high traffic. Flooring should be hard to allow for this variety. Colors should be neutral, but bright. The space should be acoustically treated to provide allow loud activities to go on without disturbing the rest of the building.

Design The M/C/A should be easily divided into (3) rooms. The room should reflect its versatile nature in the simplicity of its design.

Intention The M/C/A is intended as the principle rented space of the facility. This space may be used for wedding receptions, reunions, parties, etc and should be accessible, comfortable, dramatic and flexible enough to accommodate this wide variety of potential uses. Participants at Public Meeting 1 requested a highly flexible and "beautiful" place to hold a variety of events. This space is intended to accommodate that request. Most of the CRC centers need a larger multi-purpose room to accommodate groups of up to 200. This would be redundant in Cincinnati, with an abundance of meeting facilities throughout the city. Williams County, however, could use a new, grand facility for this use..

2.3.1 Storage

Capacity: none

Square Footage: 600

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct connection to:
Medium Meeting/Conference/Activity Room (1.2)
- Near Connection to:
Vertical circulation

Spatial Requirements:

- Securable

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- none

Use Types:

- Storage of tables, chairs, etc for Medium Meeting/Conference/Activity Room

2.4 (2) Small Classrooms

Capacity: 20-30

Square Footage: 500

Proximity Requirements:

- Near Connection to:
Vertical Circulation

Spatial Requirements:

- Generous ceiling heights
- Hard floors
- Views

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Bright
- Durability
 - allow for soft to medium uses
 - soft use – group/organization meetings
 - medium use – art/general studies classes
- Natural Light (flexible)
 - Large windows
 - controls to block out natural light when deemed appropriate

Use Types:

- After school activities
- Classes, tutoring, etc
- Group/Organization meetings
- Continuing education-type classes

Comments:

Uses Classrooms may be used for after-school activities such as tutoring, crafts, etc. The classrooms may also be used for evening GED/post-secondary classes. These may include satellite classes for the local community college.

Orientation Classrooms demand natural light, views and privacy from the rest of the facility.

Access Classrooms should be directly connected to major circulation spaces. They should be separated from the Athletic/Exercise spaces as well as the Meeting/Gathering spaces to allow for separation of activities within the facility.

Materials The materials of the classrooms should resemble an academic space.

Design Classrooms should be flexibly arranged to allow for a variety of activities.

Intention The classrooms may be used for meetings, instruction, seminars, arts, crafts, and a variety of other activities unanticipated. They should also be accessible, comfortable, dramatic and flexible enough to accommodate this wide variety of potential uses. Participants at Public Meeting 1 requested space that could accommodate music, crafts, etc. The CRC provides a minimum number of classroom type facilities, which is one of the major complaints of the directors. There seems to always be a need for more space to hold art classes, lectures, or just hold a small, private meeting. The Lincoln Community Center shows the benefit of these types of spaces, with a great deal of outreach provided to the community through these spaces. All of the CRC employees would like more, flexible, un-programmed space.

2.5 (3) Large Classrooms

Capacity: 30-40

Square Footage: 800

Proximity Requirements:

- Near Connection to:
Vertical Circulation

Spatial Requirements:

- Generous ceiling heights
- Hard floors
- Views

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Bright
- Durability
 - allow for soft to medium uses
 - soft use – group/organization meetings
 - medium use – art/general studies classes
- Natural Light (flexible)
 - Large windows
 - controls to block out natural light when deemed appropriate

Use Types:

- After school activities
- Classes, tutoring, etc
- Group/Organization meetings
- Continuing education-type classes

Comments:

Uses Classrooms may be used for after-school activities such as tutoring, crafts, etc. The classrooms may also be used for evening GED/post-secondary classes. These may include satellite classes for the local community college.

Orientation Classrooms demand natural light, views and privacy from the rest of the facility.

Access Classrooms should be directly connected to major circulation spaces. They should be separated from the Athletic/Exercise spaces as well as the Meeting/Gathering spaces to allow for separation of activities within the facility.

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2.6 Storage

Capacity: none

Square Footage: 400

Proximity Requirements:

- Near Connection to:
Classroom-size spaces (1.3)

Spatial Requirements:

- Securable

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- none

Use Types:

- storage of chairs, table, etc for classrooms

2.7 (4) Restrooms (2 Men's and 2 Women's)

Capacity: 10

Square Footage: 300

Proximity Requirements:

- Near Connection to:
Medium Meeting/Conference/Activity Room (1.2)
Classroom-size spaces (1.3)

Spatial Requirements:

- Accessible

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Clean
- Bright
- Ergonomic

Use Types:

- Restrooms

Fixture Requirements: (OBC 2902.1, No.2, E Educational Facilities)

- WC -Male/Female 3 1 per 50 (urinals=no more than 67% WC)
- Lav -Male/Female 3 1 per 50
- DF -4 1 per 100
- 1 Service Sink

Spaces Serviced:

- Meeting/Conference/Activity Room
- Small Classroom (2)
- Large Classroom (3)
- Total Occupancy serviced: **~400**

2.8 Other

3.0 Administration

3%

Administration spaces should have convenient access to all parts of the building. These spaces should be centrally located to allow a small number of people to maintain all control points. These spaces should be well appointed and well lit (naturally and artificially), creating a comfortable and pleasant working environment. These spaces should also maintain a welcoming point for visitors to the facility.

Square Footage= **1,000**

3.1 Administrator Office

Capacity: 1 + 2 guests

Square Footage: 200

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
 - Administrative Assistant (3.2)
 - Reception (3.3)
- Near Connection to:
 - Community Space (2.1)

Spatial Requirements:

- Closed office
- Space for (?) file cabinets
- (1) executive desk
- (1) desk chair
- (2) guest chairs

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Natural light
- Quality executive materials

Use Types:

- General office
- Interviews

Comments:

Uses Administration of the Community Center.

Orientation The office of the facility administrator should be provided with abundant natural light. The office should be isolated from the majority of activity in the facility to provide a greater level of privacy than the program directors.

Access The office of the administrator should be accessible only through the administration area.

Materials The material quality of the administrator's office should reflect the full-time nature of its occupancy.

Intentions The administrator will be one of a hand-full of full-time employees. This individual is charged with maintenance, staffing and coordination of the programs for the facility. According to Ms Montivon of the Lincoln Community Center, the administrator should be provided with a private office to close out the noise and get work done. The space should be connected to the administration and thereby the rest of the facility to retain a measure of control.

3.2 Program Directors

Capacity: 3

Square Footage: 400

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
 - Administrator Office (3.1)
 - Reception (3.3)
- Near Connection to:
 - Community Space (2.1)

Spatial Requirements:

- Open or closed office
- Space for (?) file cabinets
- (3) workstations
- space for copy machine, fax, etc

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Natural light
- Quality materials

Use Types:

- General office
- File keeping

Comments:

Uses This space will be occupied by a core group of individuals charged with maintaining the programs of the facility. They will keep records, calendars and programs in this area, as well as be provided work space.

Orientation These directors (probably teen, athletic and community programs) should be visually connected to the activities they are responsible for. This is to ensure that questions about a particular activity can be answered in a timely fashion, the facilities are not abused, and problems are attended to quickly. The space should be provided with abundant natural light and views.

Access The program directors should have direct access to circulation, and the various spaces and activities in use. The directors should have a direct connection with the general public.

Intention The program directors are responsible for the various activities that go on in the building, and should be "connected with their people" according to Ms Montivon. This ensures that the directors are aware of what is going on in the facility, who is there, and are available for questions or advice. The people who work there (perhaps full-time) should be afforded a high quality work environment, including natural light, and views, into the building and perhaps out, similar to the Corryville and Lincoln centers, and in contrast to the hidden administration space at the College Hill center.

3.3 Reception

Capacity: 1-2

Square Footage: 200

Proximity Requirements:

- Direct Connection to:
 - Community Space (2.1)
 - Vertical Circulation
 - All entrances
- Near Connection to:
 - Athletic/Exercise Spaces (1.0)
 - Gathering/Meeting Spaces (2.0)

Spatial Requirements:

- Open to circulation
- Information section

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

- Natural light
- Quality materials

Use Types:

- Checkpoint/control point for Athletic/Exercise Spaces
- Information
- Reservation taking

Comments:

Uses Security checkpoint for the building

Orientation The reception desk should be centrally located within the building to act as an observation point for the facility. It should be located within reach of the main entrance, and should have commanding views of any alternate entrances.

Access Reception should have access to the program directors.

Materials The reception area should be integral part of the community space, entry and administration area. Materials may reflect these three ideas, or may make some other statement regarding orientation, way-finding, etc.

Intention The reception space should be well appointed to provide the occupant with commanding views, security, and connection with the community. This point is the face of the center for every visitor, and should reflect the public, and secure, nature of the facility.

The reception desk should present more of an obstruction than in the College Hill and Coryville centers. These need a more confined entrance to control entrance. Because of the rural context of this project, the security may be less of an issue. It should still be considered that the entrance should be controlled.

3.4 Other

4.0 Service

2.5%

Service areas should be easily accessible, yet undistinguishable from the rest of the facility.

Square Footage= 1,100

4.1 Custodial Office

Capacity: 1

Square Footage: 200

Proximity Requirements:

-Easy connection to all spaces

Spatial Requirements:

-(?) File cabinets

-Desk and chair

-Tool storage

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

-Natural Light

-Durability

Use Types:

-File storage

-Records keeping

4.2 (3) Janitorial Storage

Capacity: none

Square Footage: 100

Proximity Requirements:

-Easy connection to all spaces

Spatial Requirements:

-(1) storage per floor

Aesthetic/Material Requirements:

-none

Use Types:

-Storage of cleaning supplies

4.3 HVAC

Square Footage: 600

4.4 Loading Dock

Square Footage: 200

4.5 Other

5.0 Other

1%

4.0 Precedents

In the last several years, municipalities have again become interested in providing their residents with places that facilitate gathering and make a rejuvenating effort in their communities. These places, especially recently, have been designed with a particular effort toward an expression of the potential of the community, and are designed in an effort to promote a sense of *community* through the way people use them. Elements of these most recent examples from architectural literature and examples from the Cincinnati Recreation Commission provide the architectural precedents for the Montpelier Community Center.

The Corryville and College Hill Recreation Centers, built by the Cincinnati Recreation Commission provide contemporary examples of a public community outreach, both in design and programming. The issues raised by these facilities, positive and negative, have informed many of the planning and aesthetic decisions for this project. The Lincoln Community Center provides a unique look into the work of a project similar to this one: a community recreation center, making use of a sizable addition to an existing building. The security issues from this precedent have been especially helpful in the planning of this project.

First, however, it is important to demonstrate the facilities that are currently available to the residents of the community. The Williams County Family YMCA is the only indoor recreation facility in the Williams County. This examination provides a look into this 15 year old private facility.

Williams County Family YMCA (1988), Bryan, OH

The Williams County YMCA (YMCA) is the only public, indoor recreation facility in Williams County. The facility is primarily dependant on grants from the national YMCA association, and proceeds from memberships. Members come from all over the County, but most are residents of the county seat, Bryan.

The YMCA was introduced to the County as a public recreation facility. The program includes a pool, gymnasium with other accessory spaces, and several multi-purpose activity spaces. Its unique place in the community makes the YMCA a well-used facility, with an average of 150 users per day.

The YMCA is located in the Moore Memorial Park complex. It is not located on a secondary arterial road into Bryan, without a convincing public presence. While it serves the community, and has developed programs to reach out to the community, the YMCA does not serve as direct participant in community activities. It is privately funded, and is open only to paid members and their guests.

3.1 YMCA, Entrance
(Photo by author)

Entrance- The YMCA makes use of a single entrance accessible directly from the at-grade parking lot. The considerable walk from the parking to the entrance is generally unprotected (Fig. 3.1). Walk-ins constitute a small number of members because of the remote location of the facility.

The central administration point controls access to the facility and includes an observation point for the aquatics area. All of the athletic facilities are accessed from this point, with a separate entrance serving the multi-purpose spaces.

Aquatics (Pool)- The aquatics spaces of the YMCA are a central part of the function of the facility. While the mass of the pool is a dominant part of the elevation, its use is undifferentiated in the detailing of the building.

The main space is large, with a lofty exposed roof structure. A series of glass block openings allow natural light into the space. These openings are low and do not overcome the large dark volume. Hard, white surfaces help to brighten the space. The individual aquatic types include a lap pool, wading pool, whirlpool and saunas accessible through the adult locker rooms only.

Locker Rooms- Locker rooms are divided between adult and family spaces for both sexes to allow for more diverse uses. These connect directly with the pool to allow for easy access, but also serve the gymnasium and racketball courts which share the central corridor. The locker rooms are large to accommodate a very full facility.

3.2 Aquatics Space
(Photo by author)

3.3 Locker Room
(Photo by author)

3.4 Raquetball Court
(Photo by author)

Racketball Courts- Courts are accessible only after having checked in at administration. They are simply planned to meet space requirements, and make use of a reinforced glass wall to allow for spectators (fig. 3.4). The courts provide no access to the outside, views or light.

Gymnasium- The gymnasium plays host to a large variety of activities. Most obviously, the two basketball courts are regularly used for youth and adult league games. During the day, the gymnasium is used by several regular groups: professionals before work and at lunch, second and third shift workers, and various pick-up groups. Other activities that use the gymnasium include an aerobics class, indoor soccer, and t-ball.

The gymnasium is entirely artificially lit, and is not air conditioned. The latter element is considered a problem in the warm summer months. The lack of climate control, however, does not seem to diminish the use of the facility. A walking track circles the gymnasium (fig. 3.6), accessible from the corridor. Twelve laps around the track equal a mile. Above the corridor and locker rooms, at the west end of the track, a weight and workout area serves the adult membership.

Multi-purpose (Activity) Rooms- One large room serves as the “Activity Room”, capable of seating over 200 people. The space is designed to be divided by fixed partitions into four smaller spaces. Only the northern-most space has access to the outside, and

3.5 Gymnasium
(Photo by author)

3.6 Walking Track and workout space
(Photo by author)

3.7 Multi-purpose Room
(Photo by author)

natural light. This space is permanently reserved for day care and pre-school activities (fig. 3.7). The floor is tile, receiving mixed reactions from the regular users. Those who work with children would like carpeting to better accommodate play. However, the tile allows for easier cleanup.

The Activity rooms are used for parties and receptions as well as ball room dancing lessons, CPR recertification classes, and the like. Rental is usually limited to members. The kitchen is used for the daycare and pre-school activities, causing a conflict with rentals. As a result, receptions, etc are only permitted the use of a kitchenette (fig. 3.9).

Aesthetics (Interior)- Interior finishes vary from drywall in the activity and day care spaces, to painted cmu in the administration and aquatics space. Color is use sparingly, mostly isolated to the corridor in the activity and day care wing (fig. 3.10). These colors were added only recently with a donation from a local paint distributor. The color were selected by the day care children.

Aesthetics (Exterior)- Exterior statements are highly restrained.

3.8 Kitchenette (Photo by author)

3.9 Activity/Daycare corridor (Photo by author)

3.10 Activity Wing (Photo by author)

3.11 Aquatics Wing (Photo by author)

As mentioned previously, the building has very little street presence. The portion of the building that is visible from the street is not one of architectural significance (fig. 3.11). Colors on the exterior are limited to the brick and the off-white metal (fig. 3.1). Limited plantings attempt to humanize the restrained entrance.

The YMCA is an important part of the community of Bryan. A bus service from the city's schools brings member children to play at the end of the day. The pool is the home of the Bryan High School and Jr. High School swim teams. The Bryan Hospital uses the pool for various rehabilitation activities. Local senior citizens hold pot-lucks and other activities in the multi-purpose rooms. Holidays and other times of the year see the YMCA open to the public for events in conjunction with the Park department and other groups. Its location does not match this presence in the community. While the site allows for a great deal of parking and a large footprint, the building is relatively secluded from the majority of life in Bryan.

Its appearance likewise fails to represent the community in any convincing way. Its drab exterior plays down its unique civic connection. The low levels of natural lighting or connection with the site negates the beautiful surroundings that make the site desirable. All of the activity rooms should have exterior windows looking into the park to brighten the spaces and provide a feeling of connection with the community. The pool and gymnasium would both benefit from the natural light provided by.

While the YMCA is an active member of the community in Bryan, it does not promote *community* in the city. By requiring a membership, and focusing primarily on athletic facilities, the YMCA fills a select need in the community. This limited scope makes the multi-purpose spaces nearly useless for a majority of the time, and limits the chance interactions of the community as a whole. While preventing the opportunity to create a "hood hangout", the YMCA has limited its impact by limiting the flexibility of the facility.

Corryville Recreation Center (1998), Cincinnati, OH

Designed by Speer & Speer, Architects of Cincinnati, the Corryville Recreation Center serves all age groups in the uptown area to the east of the University of Cincinnati. A tour was provided by Margaret Ahlrichs, director of the Center.

An important aspect of the Center was its intended use as a before- and after-school daycare facility for school age children. This meant for a high level of scrutiny from both local and state agencies in the design and execution of the facility. College Hill Recreation Center (discussed later) was intended for the same sort of use.

The building is organized along a central double-loaded corridor (fig. 3.16). This corridor serves as common space for the building, with large clerestory windows providing abundant natural light in this space (fig. 3.13,14). Ms. Ahlrichs finds this to be one of the most appealing aspects of the center. "It is a pleasure to be in a well-designed architectural space." The abundance of natural light makes the space bright, even on a cloudy day.

An important aspect of the Corryville Recreation Center is its flexibility. Nearly all furniture is purchased with wheels, and the major meeting spaces are large, simply planned spaces. However, some activities require more specialized spaces, like pottery. Clay "throwing" requires a pottery wheel which is required by code to have a separate room. Ms. Ahlrichs would like to include more specialized activities like pottery in her schedule. The Center averages 150-200 visitors per day.

3.12 Corryville Recreation Center (Photos by author)

3.13 Central double-loaded corridor

3.14 Section of corridor

3.15 Art Classroom

Entrance- An important asset to the Corryville Recreation Center is the parking directly accessible to the entrance. The Eden Ave entrance is the only door that is not alarmed, forcing visitors to enter by the reception desk. Set at the east end of the central corridor, the reception desk provides the control point for the entire building. One person at this point has a commanding view of the entrances to all classrooms, locker rooms and the main entrance to the gymnasium.

Dance Studio- "Worth its weight in gold". According to Ms. Ahlrichs (who worked with Speer & Speer during the design phase), the dance studio was an essential part of the original concept. While it had not been included in previous buildings of similar use, it has been included in all recreation centers built by the CRC since. The dance studio is equipped with a floating wood floor which decreases injuries of the participants. Mirrors and a dance rail were included in the space on the south wall.

3.16 Diagrammatic Floor Plan (by author)

3.17 Dance Studio

Kitchen- Every element of the kitchen is lockable to “prevent casual browsing”. The kitchen at the Corryville Recreation Center is used for everything from cooking classes to 200-person meals.

Gymnasium- The main entrance for the gymnasium is located near the reception desk for easy observation. The gymnasium can also be accessed through the locker rooms, but these doors can be locked to restrict movement. A great deal of natural light is introduced into the gymnasium through the large clerestory windows on the north side of the space (fig. 3.18).

3.18 Gymnasium, north wall

Storage- Moveable storage is also a key player in the makeup of the Center. Medium sized, lockable shelf modules on wheels provide the vehicle by which art supplies and other smaller articles can be moved from room to room depending on the use.

Aesthetics (Interior)- Exposed concrete block walls and stained concrete floors provide a low maintenance, easy-to-clean environment. To counter the looming, massive feel that these materials present, large clerestory windows bring natural light into the central corridor. Unfortunately, this great use of natural light is not afforded the majority of the spaces in the building.

Aesthetics (Exterior)- The essential element of the exterior aesthetics is the impressive street presence achieved with the use of the curving wall of the dance studio. The glass curtain wall faces

3.19 Kitchen

3.20 Workout Space

northeast and the intersection of University and Eden Avenues (figs. 3.12, 21). This view into the building “acts as a stage” for the Center. According to Ms. Ahlrichs, passersby often stop to inquire about the programs offered at the Center after seeing an activity underway in the Dance Studio.

Several elements of the design of this facility have influenced the development of the Montpelier Community Center. First, the center's street presence makes it a highly visible element of the community. This concept keeps the center in the public eye, for support and security. The use of the “stage” of the dance studio as a connection to the public ensures transparency and a connection through its function.

The central corridor allows for easy monitoring of the facility. While extensive clerestories in this space provide abundant, secure natural light, the narrow corridor does not provide effective space for gathering, preventing its regular use as a common space. The use of highly durable interior materials throughout the building allows for extended life of the facility, while allowing some flexibility with respect to color and texture.

3.21 Entrance and curved glass wall

3.22 Built-in display

College Hill Recreation Center (2002), Cincinnati, OH

Designed by Moody/Nolan, Ltd, the College Hill Recreation Center opened in August 2002. The Center serves College Hill, an “inner suburb” of Cincinnati. It is located next to Aiken High School and serves a large senior citizen base including the Twin Towers Retirement Community. A tour was provided by Rick Schroer.

Similar to the Corryville Recreation Center, the College Hill Recreation Center is organized along a central common space. More than a corridor, this space connects all of the major elements of the Center, adding dramatic views into the wooded site. The Center is unique in its open-plan approach to serving its community. The community gymnasium and workout area are connected to the central common space (fig. 3.25) by wide, largely unrestricted views.

The College Hill Recreation Center is one of the busiest such facilities in the city, offering a large variety of activities. An additional bonus was the inclusion of a second gymnasium for joint use by Aiken High School and the Center and a walking track suspended above the gymnasiums (fig. 3.24).

The Center is open an average of 100 hours and serves nearly 2,000 visitors per week. A major use of the Center is a day camp for kindergarten-age children. Most of the visitors during the day are senior citizens, using the walking track and workout facilities. After school, the gymnasiums fill up with practice and pick-up games.

3.23 College Hill Recreation Center
(Photos by author)

3.24 Community gymnasium with walking track above

Entrance- Important for the entrance is one point of entry. This allows for consistent monitoring of visitors entering the facility. One desire of the staff at the Center is more control of the entrance. This could be achieved through the use of a rotunda or other such container to force visitors directly into contact with the reception desk.

Day Camp- One problem with the Center's day camp space is its extensive curving glass wall (fig. 3.26). This north-facing wall makes the room "always cold". One recommendation is to face the room to the south, or make the windows smaller.

Administration- Part of the administration core is the Community Council's office. This body is the local version of the City Council, and works with local groups. Having this office as a part of the Center keeps it "plugged-in" to the community. All of the directors (six of them) have space in the administration area. In the center of the building, the directors have no access to views or natural light.

Multi-purpose Room- The multi-purpose room is designed to be divided into three separate rooms. The partitions do not isolate these spaces well, making the idea of multiple activities undesirable. The tracks for these partitions are low, making the open room feel confined (fig. 3.27).

Each of the three potential divisions of the multi-purpose room

3.25 Diagrammatic Floor Plan (By author)

3.26 Day Camp glass wall (left) and entrance (right)

3.27 Multi-purpose Room

make use of a unique glass wall to create views. The rooms look out onto the wooded site. A “community patio” is planned for the site just outside of these rooms (fig. 3.28). The current room seats 150 banquet-style, but is recommended to be planned larger (200+) to accommodate larger groups. The Center is usually host to 3-4 groups every weekend.

Kitchen- The kitchen attached to the multi-purpose room is fitted out for catering or cooking. All elements are commercial. Two serving windows are included in the kitchen. The left window opens into a corner of the multi-purpose room. The right window opens into the corridor and has been used for concessions.

Dance Studio- The dance space was developed as a result of the inclusion of a similar space in the Corryville Recreation Center. The space is equipped with a floating floor and mirror wall (fig. 3.31). Windows on the southeast wall look out onto the wooded site. Activities that have used the space include dance, tae kwon do, and various other physical activities.

3.28 “Community Patio”

3.29 View into gym

3.30 Exterior of Workout Space

3.31 Dance Studio

Workout Area- The workout space in the Center is open to the common space (fig. 3.29). According to Mr. Schroer, this creates a positive “community feel” in which to workout. The space also includes large windows that look out onto the site (fig. 3.30). The view created by this connection to the site draws the visitor through the common space to look over the rail into the workout space.

Gymnasium/Walking Track- The College Hill Recreation Center is the only CRC facility to incorporate an indoor walking track. The track is primarily used by the large senior citizen community. The open orientation to the common space allows for easy observation by staff, and provides the same “community feel” as the workout space (fig. 3.29). The gymnasiums are more than adequately lit by south facing clerestory windows (fig. 3.24).

Essential to the planning of the College Hill gymnasiums was the inclusion of moveable stands. These stands have been used in all parts of the building for various activities, and have even been moved outside to allow for large events in the gymnasiums. “You can put them where you need them.” Other well planned elements include large volumes of storage for both gymnasiums, scoreboards for both sides of the venue, and net dividers at mid-court.

Aesthetics (Interior)- Color is much more liberally used at College Hill than at Corryville. Carpet is used throughout the common space (high traffic area). Natural light and views were a high priority for all rooms in the Center. This is encouraged by the highly natural site characteristics that surround it. Each of the major spaces is oriented to capture the best possible view. The use of an open structure is useful for opening up the ceiling in the major spaces. The use of dropped artificial lighting provides an effective finished feeling, even in the more refined spaces: multi-purpose room, dance studio, etc. (figs. 3.27 & 3.31).

Aesthetics (Exterior)- The Belmont Ave. façade (front) is a very restrained, uniform, brick veneer (fig. 3.23). The entrance is indicated by a vertical glass element, and flanked by a metal canopy. The canopy element provides a convenient place to

3.32 Privacy Wall

wait in the shade or under cover from rain or snow. This elevation extends beyond the building envelop to the south providing a measure of privacy for the planned community patio (fig. 3.32).

The College Hill Recreation Center provides a bright and inviting facility for recreation and community involvement. The effective use of the site makes for dramatic views and interesting spatial relationships. The use of color and light has a very positive effect on the interior of the building. More natural light throughout the central common space would have been even more beneficial.

Combined with the physical and visual connection to the gymnasium, the common space is an effective hub of activity for the center. Its flexibility and abundant size make it an effective connector between spaces while allowing for informal gathering and chance meetings within the space. As the heart of the center, it has the potential to serve as the social and civic crossroad of the community.

Lincoln Community Center (2003), Cincinnati, OH

Designed by WA Architects, the Lincoln Community Center (LCC) opened in June 2003. The Center is part of the West End area of downtown Cincinnati, and serves a primarily low-income neighborhood. To encourage the revitalization of the area through new low- and medium-income housing, the Cincinnati Metropolitan Housing Authority (CMHA) spent over \$2.5 million to improve the LCC. The facility was then returned to the CRC.

LCC is unique in that it incorporates an old facility (ca. 1940) with its pre-existing elements into one contemporary rivaling its contemporaries already discussed. The original building (fig. 53) included classrooms, a gymnasium and weight training/workout facilities. These uses were retained, but most were moved to allow for improved efficiency of use.

The 2003 addition is built at grade and includes a new gymnasium, locker rooms, weight training/workout facilities and a new entrance and administration hub. A series of monumental ramps were employed to accessibly connect the new to the old (fig. 3.34). A tour was provided by LCC's director, Sharon Montivon.

3.33 Lincoln Community Center: original building (left), addition (right) (Photos by author)

3.34 Ramp Atrium

Administration- According to Ms. Montivon, observation is a major problem for the LCC. With (effectively) three floors of center, it is impossible to casually keep an eye on everyone in the building. The central administration assists in the security of the building, handling visitors from both front and back entrances.

The reception desk has a view of both entrances as well as the ramp atrium (fig. 3.35). From this point, a view of the street is provided by large windows north of the main entrance (fig. 3.40).

Behind the reception desk, and large windows, the program coordinators have been given space. These four full-time staff members also have a view of the main entrance, ramp atrium and the reception desk. "The fish bowl" provides a positive connection between the coordinators and "their people". The director's office is located in the basement to provide some privacy.

Gymnasium- The gymnasium is a dramatic space with a high, vaulted roof, the structure of which is left exposed. At the north and south ends, this vault is opened with clerestory windows, allowing a great deal of natural light into the space. While inspiring, the direct light from the south causes some glare problems on the court floor (fig. 3.36).

The single-court gymnasium can be split using the motorized curtain. Capacity in the gymnasium was set at 60, apparently because of the number of bleacher seating provided. This is a hitch for planning as the room's area could accommodate more.

Classrooms- Retained from the original building, the

3.35 New reception

3.36 New Gymnasium

classrooms are used for pre-school activities and outside groups. A smaller classroom is used by the Cincinnati Public Schools for a pre-expulsion program (fig. 3.37). This group meets with two teachers during the school day.

The larger classroom above is used by the CMHA for a school-aged day care. Addition space in the original building is allocated for a computer lab for the CMHA use, and a meeting room for use by the Center.

Teen Lounge- A large portion of the basement of the original building is allocated to the teen lounge (fig. 3.38). This space is the envy of all of the newer facilities for its size. The large space allows for a more comfortable arrangement of uses, including pool tables, television and computers. These are sufficiently separated to allow multiple activities at once.

Aesthetics (Interior)- The original building retains much of its original drab colors and materials. The interior masonry walls are mostly retained except where doors were filled in, etc.

The addition makes greater use of color and form than the old.

3.37 Pre-existing classroom used by CMHA

3.38 Teen Lounge

3.39 Ramp atrium detail

3.40 Glass projections on Linn St

The greatest use of color is focused on the reception and administration areas, where large blue tile, red counter top and blue lockers enliven the mostly white drywall space. The new gymnasium uses the sound dampening to introduce a great deal of color (fig. 3.36).

While generally simple, the ramp atrium is by far the most dramatic space. The skylight above highlights the previous Linn St elevation of the old gymnasium (fig. 3.39). This sets the addition apart, allowing a great deal of natural light and the feeling of two heavy masses set just apart.

Aesthetics (Exterior)- The architectural expression of the addition to the LCC unmistakably contrasts the old. The original plain brick building is marginalized by the lofty bright white of the ramp atrium and the glass at the entrance and workout room. The original building seems almost as if it were a different use, but for “Lincoln Community Center” emblazoned above the old entrance. The addition is dominated on Linn St by the ramp atrium. A ribbon of windows runs at the angle of the interior ramp (fig. 3.33), providing the basis for the large, angled block on the exterior. This block provides a transition, aesthetically as well as functionally, between the drab brick original and the lofty addition.

Beyond the block, the main entrance begins a new vocabulary, one of glass. The large openings provide a more than adequate light for the spaces inside, and provide a visual connection with the community on the street.

At the rear of the building, the addition is less concealing (fig.

3.41 Linn St elevation

3.42 LCC rear elevation, multi-purpose room behind large windows at center

3.43 LCC addition at rear

3.42). More of the original building is left exposed, providing direct natural light for the renovated gymnasium. From the rear, a better view of the gymnasium is made possible (fig. 3.43). This is clad in deeply corrugated metal. The vaulted roof provides a unifying cap for the building.

The LCC is particularly relevant to this investigation as a contemporary community center addition. The reorientation of the entrance to the addition allowed for accessible entry and a new administration and observation point. This centralized point allows for effective observation of the addition, but its separation from the original building prevents observation in this area.

The use of the ramp system to connect the addition and original building provides a unique and effective element for the center. As a space, the ramp atrium is dramatic and has influenced the vertical circulation of the Montpelier Community Center. Functionally, however, the atrium breaks up the flow of the complex. This break, as mentioned earlier, is a hurdle for security concerns, and is addressed through a more generous and open atrium that intersects the original building in the Montpelier Community Center.

Red Hook Center for the Arts (2000), Brooklyn, NY¹

Designed by Hanrahan + Meyers of New York, the Red Hook Center for the Arts is an urban renovation project that attempts to infuse life and color into its community. The addition works to simplify the entry sequence and reorganizes the interior to accommodate community and art facilities.

According to the architects, it was important to develop a more accessible and personable presence to the community. The “entry pavilion” replaces the original monumental stairs and entry with a brightly colored, multi-story space and houses the vertical circulation. The lower floor of the building was reclaimed from an alternative high school to be occupied by the arts and community facilities.

An important element related to this project is the intentional connection of the interior to the context. The street elevation (fig. 6.63) uses a “scaled-up window wall, ‘presenting’ to passersby the activity within.”² The window wall looks into the entry pavilion and the main circulation space. The views into the building are continued in the back of the building, where a giant window allows views into the gymnasium from the neighborhood (fig. 6.65). These were intended as “stages” for display or performance and as safe places to gather.¹

3.44 Street Elevation, Red Hook Center for the Arts (Photos by Eduard Hueber)

3.45 Schematic digital model (existing in gray, additions in green) (From Hanrahan + Meyers Architects)

3.46 View out from the gymnasium

¹ Hanrahan + Meyers Architects (2002). *The Four States of Architecture*. London: John Wiley and Sons. p 36.

² Russell, James S. “Red Hook Center for the Arts”. *Architectural Record*, 2001 Mar., v. 189, n. 3, pp 136-139.

Hunts Point Community Center (2001), The Bronx, NY³

Also designed by Hanrahan + Meyers of New York, the Hunts Point Community Center is an object in the relatively barren landscape of a city park. The building uses glass and a unique form to create a welcoming haven for an inner-city community. This is continued on the interior with a spacious and flexible plan.⁴

From the exterior, Hanrahan + Meyers use a great deal of glass to create an inviting appearance for the building. To prevent the glass from becoming a security problem, the architects used a folding airplane-hangar door to protect the windows at night and canopy during the day (fig. 3.67). Above, the great expanses of glass provide a bright and open feeling for the occupants. Natural light is also provided using by two great light scoops on the roof (fig. 3.68). These make a highly choreographed statement on the interior. To cut down on the cost, the roof form makes use of a standardized roof truss (fig. 3.69). This long span allows for the very open and flexible interior which is only accented the glass.

The large, open space and the use of a standardized roof structure to accomplish a relatively complex form provide a valid precedent for my project. These combined with abundant natural light provide an open space for recreation. As with the Red Hook Center for the Arts, the dual use of the gymnasium as an auditorium accommodates a variety of activities.

3.47 Entrance (Photos by Peter Aaron)

3.48 Folding doors

3.49 Diagram of roof and light scoops (From Hanrahan + Meyers Architects)

3.50 Interior and roof

³ Hanrahan + Meyers Architects (2002). *The Four States of Architecture*. London: John Wiley and Sons. p 102.

⁴ Pearson, Clifford A. "Hunts Point Community Center". *Architectural Record*, 2003 Mar., v. 190, n.3, p.120-123.

Joslyn Art Museum (1994), Omaha, Nebraska⁵

The new wing of the Joslyn Art Museum Sir Norman Foster and Partners is a sizable, yet sensitive addition to an historic Art Deco building. The addition takes certain elements of the building and adapts them to Foster's minimalist vocabulary, while introducing a new and interesting transition.

The addition is essentially a windowless box which matches the original building in height, elevation and material. The marble used to clad the addition is from the same quarry as the original, but is laid in a stack bond to differentiate the two.

Between the original and the addition, Foster introduces a glass link. The link separates the new from the old, stepping back from the marble buildings to prevent competition. The element subtly contrasts the masonry buildings to introduce a transition between new and old, and a new accessible entrance.

This link is an important example of the possibilities for the addition proposed for this project. Adding a contrasting element between two nearly uniform masses creates opportunities for transition, the introduction of natural light, and a new vocabulary to enliven the elevation.

3.51 Main Elevation
(Photos by Patrick Drickey)

3.52 Building Section

⁵ Myerson, Jeremy (1996). *New Public Architecture*. London: Laurence King Publishing. pp156-159.

British Museum (2001), London⁶

Sir Norman Foster and Partners developed a unique solution to enclose the great court at the heart of the British Museum that both creates a great public space in the heart of the building, and gracefully touches the existing building.

Foster's roof is a self-supported web of steel that suspends the outside far out of the reach of the people on the ground. It does so without interfering with the original cornice. This graceful enclosure preserves the existing building, encloses the great court and only injects its own identity through the shadows it casts on the pristine limestone walls.

3.53 Queen Elizabeth II Great Court Atrium (Photo by Nigel Young)

3.54 Building Section

⁶ Hart, Sara. "British Museum". *Architectural Record*, 2001 Mar., v. 189, n. 3, pp 114-121.

5.0 The Solution

A solution proposed for the Village of Montpelier is a community recreation center in the model of those built in the last 5 years by the Cincinnati Recreation Commission. Because the design is incomplete at this time, this section will describe the important ideas that make up the design of the facility. First, the elements of the existing building that are to be demolished will be discussed, and the reasons for their removal. Second, the impact of the site strategy on the building's influence will be discussed. The building's principle elevation (civic elevation) along Main Street will be discussed in terms of its influence in portraying the importance of the project and its place in the community. Finally, the internal organization of the building and its relationship to the ideas of *community* will be described.

Site 1: Existing Site Conditions (Map by author from aerial photo by Williams County Engineer)
04/07

5.1 Demolition

After the site was selected, the next step was to determine how much of the existing building to save. This was primarily driven by accessibility concerns from the original building, use of a portion of the site for parking, the preservation of the existing Main Street elevation, and the proposed uses of the facility. Additional consideration was made for the adaptability of building elements. It was decided to propose the demolition of the 1960 addition, most of the gymnasium addition and the auditorium wing of the original building.

The 1960 addition is not connected to the original building accessibly, using a narrow stair connection to the north stair of the original building. The building's placement on the site creates a courtyard which is too small to use, and really provides more square footage than is necessary for the facility. Its use of the site is highly inefficient, and would be better appropriated to on-site parking for the facility.

5.1 Aerial Photo of existing high school, looking west. (Photo by Al Benjamin)

The connection between gymnasium and auditorium wing is equally inaccessible for people with disabilities. Because the gymnasium itself is in good shape, and a necessary part of the program, at least the floor and footprint of the building should be saved. The locker rooms are also inaccessible, and should be removed to provide more play space, or storage for the facility.

The auditorium is a large room with a great deal of potential. However, at the center of the complex, it presents another accessibility problem, and a redundancy to the gymnasium for a large (occasionally used) multi-purpose space, and the large study hall space in the original building. Its use as an auditorium would be redundant in the community as the new K-12 complex includes an auditorium. The removal of the original auditorium would open the center of the site to potential building and site development.

Four houses line the west side of the block containing the site of the high school campus. These buildings, three of which are tenant occupied, crowd the existing gymnasium, and limit the expansion of the building. The demolition of these four houses, while not essential to the project, allows more freedom in the use of the block, and sets up the same prominence for the site afforded other important civic buildings in the community and county, namely the County Courthouse Square, and that of Montpelier's Village Hall.

5.2 Williams County Courthouse Square ca. 1900. (Williams County Historical Society)

5.3 Montpelier Village Hall. (Photo by author)

Pedestrian Path

A ceremonial path is necessary to encourage a sense of pedestrian connection between the downtown, community center and fairgrounds. This path should take the form of a promenade: broad, smooth pavement; shade trees; seating at intervals; etc. The path may terminate at the "Gateway", or continue through the Historic Downtown to the Village Hall, the center of civic government. This provides the opportunity for further demarcation at the western terminus of the path.

Area of Intervention

The area of intervention focuses on the sites of the existing public library and the proposed community center.

Existing sidewalks along Main Street are mostly 5 feet wide and concrete. Trees along the street are a mix of occasional old growth (30 years+) and highly sporadic new ornamental trees.

New sidewalks should be wider (around 8 feet) to accommodate a larger number of pedestrians, and paved using more aesthetic and uniform means. Old trees should remain, and new trees should be planted continuously at regular intervals from the County Fairgrounds to the Historic Downtown.

Existing
Proposed

Marker

A point of reference for visitors to the village. This marker is intended to catch the attention of drivers as they pass the intervention, and encourage them to investigate the community's center.

Gateway

A symbolic gateway to the central business district. This element would mark the transition of the commercial heart of the village and its residential core. This element may mark the end of the transitional path.

Pedestrian Gate

A new pedestrian entrance for the County Fairgrounds to encourage better connection with the village.

Pedestrian Path

The pedestrian path should make use of small scale elements to encourage walking along Main Street. Regularly spaced benches, human-scale street lights, ornamental trees, like those used in the rest of the historic core, should be used to create a promenade-type environment. The fixtures (benches, lights, etc) should be selected to match those proposed by the Downtown Montpelier Revitalization Committee in order to visually extend this area toward the County Fairgrounds. For this reason, the fixtures will be historic in appearance.

Section through Main Street at Residential Area

Elements (furniture, paving patterns, details) should be continued from the historic downtown's revitalization. Street lights are tall, and reflect the historic character intended by the village's revitalization committee. Benches and other furnishings are to be of recycled plastic timber. Paving will be pressed, colored concrete in a hearing bone pattern.

Marker

A point of reference for visitors to the village. The marker may take the form of a signal, shelter, or sign. In any case, it should act as an extension of the design of the community center. The marker must be large enough to catch the eye of drivers and passengers driving/riding along Main Street, and direct their attention toward the new facility. It must be small enough to allow mostly unobstructed views of the building from the street. The marker should also act as an integral part of the "Pedestrian Path", either as a gate for the center, simply a place to rest along the way.

Gateway

Symbolic gateway to the central business district. Using planters, walls or other such devices, the gateways should mark the east and west ends of the historic downtown, as well as the western end of the pedestrian path. The elements should make use of materials and massing similar to the "Marker" to provide a reference for passersby.

Pedestrian Gate

In order to tie the Williams County Fairgrounds into the new pedestrian pathway, a dedicated pedestrian connection is needed. This gate would be best applied to the Main Street and River Street corner of the Fairgrounds, and should use a language similar to that of the "Marker" and "Gateway" to express its part of the procession. The gate should be appropriately scaled to reflect its part at an end to the pathway, and as the symbolic gate for the Fairgrounds.

Map 3b: Proposed Path and Markers

04/22

Pedestrian Path

The pedestrian path acts as the southern edge of the Community Center site, the main pedestrian access for the Center, and boundary between street and park. The "Marker" acts as the portal for the Center from the Pedestrian Path.

Section through Main Street at Community Center

In this area, the path acts as an accent to the existing infrastructure by merely replacing the sidewalk. The path continues here in order to complete the visual connection between the three major elements of the village.

Section through Main Street at Historic Downtown

The pedestrian path should extend beyond the gate at the County Fairgrounds in order to fully engage this major aspect of the community. Proposed amenities replace a chain link fence along the sidewalk, and add ornamental trees and vendor locations along the Fairgrounds side of the street.

Section through Main Street at County Fairgrounds

Map 3c: Proposed Path and Markers

05/03

Slow Zone

A "slow zone" should be used to encourage slower traffic speeds along Main Street, especially through the downtown and at the proposed Community Center. This could entail the development of a boulevard or the use of brick or other textured materials, especially at crosswalks. These sorts of elements are being planned for the "revitalization" of downtown, but should be expanded to the proposed community center to tie the two areas together and promote pedestrian access.

Area of Intervention

The area of intervention focuses on the sites of the existing public library and the proposed community center.

Currently, Main Street is highly traveled by tractor-trailers, most of which travel at high speeds. Paving is uniform through the community, which only lends itself to higher speeds.

More aesthetic interventions at crosswalks could help to tie the pavement into a more holistic approach to Main Street's appearance. The material should identify itself with the material used on the "Pedestrian Path" connecting the County Fairgrounds and Downtown.

Existing
Proposed

Fair Shuttle

To further draw Fair visitors into the village, a shuttle may be introduced to transport them along Main Street. The shuttle may follow a route similar to that shown to best demonstrate the assets of the Main Street corridor.

Economic Development

Previous community expansions, especially at the municipal park, have resulted in a small measure of commercial expansion. This should be anticipated and limited to the specified area to prevent haphazard or excessive growth.

Historic Character

Development should be restricted in the indicated areas to preserve the existing historic character of Main Street.

5.2 Site Strategy

From the beginning of the process of design, it was important to base the new portion of the building on the existing. The site strategy was to reflect the geometric organization of the existing site and buildings to exhibit a prominence similar to the “courthouse square model” as described above. This strategy is part of a larger, more comprehensive intention for the entire Main Street Corridor. Maps 3 and 4 exhibit a proposal for a civic corridor to be developed along Main Street, between the County Fairgrounds and the Historic Downtown.

Map 3: The corridor is intended to tie the major elements of Main Street (downtown, fairgrounds and proposed community center) together to form a more cohesive community expression. At the midpoint of this corridor, the community center has the opportunity to play a role in the connection of the community, and thereby the downtown to the only destination in the village for visitors.

A major part of the proposal is the introduction of a paved promenade along the north side of Main Street. This pedestrian friendly path would provide a wide, uniform route by which visitors and residents could make the walk along the corridor.

Key elements along this route are intended to provide a visual impetus for pedestrians to explore the path provided. At the east end of the path is a proposed pedestrian gate for the fairgrounds. This gate would provide a more convenient entrance from the majority of the village to the south and west, and a direct connection to Main Street. At the community center, a pavilion or other marker would provide the pedestrian with a break and welcome them to visit the village's social and cultural heart. A gateway to the downtown would welcome both pedestrian and driver to the economic potential for the village.

Map 4: Improvements to the street would encourage drivers to slow down, using texture to denote important pedestrian areas. These “slow zones” would correspond with the important sections of the corridor, downtown and the community center. Clearly demarcated crosswalks in these areas would help to provide a more pedestrian friendly environment. Improved and expanded surface parking around the community center and downtown could help to promote activity in these areas.

Based on the example of the Maywood Restaurant at the perimeter of the Municipal Park, a regularly used community facility creates the potential for commercial development in the area. This should be planned for and permitted at a level that is appropriate for the historic residential neighborhood as shown. Finally, a shuttle may be introduced to further encourage visitors to expand into the village from the Fair. The route for this shuttle should focus on Main Street and engage the landmarks along the corridor: Village Hall, downtown, the community center and the Fairgrounds.

Site 2: Proposed Site Improvements (Map by author from aerial photo by Williams County Engineer)
04/24

Site 2: The existing “Front Yard” of the high school is expanded to North Harrison Street. This extension leaves the building unobscured from the Public Library, and the intersection of Harrison and Main Streets and presents the elevation of the building from Harrison Street to East Avenue. This presentation allows the building to advertise itself to the public (and visitors) architecturally and, as described earlier, it also gives the building the same prominence on its site provided Village Hall and the County Courthouse, recognizing its potential importance for the village. The resulting visual connection between the Center and the Public Library allows for the free movement of students between the two facilities. The expanded space accentuates the “void” presented along Main Street, interrupting the residential district.

By providing an entrance to the building on the Main Street elevation, the “front-yard” allows events inside to spill onto the lawn. Space is provided immediately outside the Main Street entrance for just such allowances. This capability provides a needed level of organization to the yard, and the variety of hard, medium and soft surfaces allows for a variety of activities to take place in this area. Such activities could include: concerts, receptions, photo opportunities, speeches, etc.

The north side of the block is retained for parking. The current arrangement provides only 14 parking spaces on site. The

5.4 Initial phasing diagram.

5.5 Schematic sketch showing organization of “Front-Yard”

placement of the parking behind the building obscures it and allows for a highly orchestrated public presentation of the building along Main Street. The expanded, and re-organized, parking acts as the first stage of a parking strategy to accommodate the variety of uses in the facility. It also provides a generous drop-off area and entrance for users who have driven.

The entrance to the building facing the parking (north) would certainly be the primary entrance for the building, and is treated accordingly. Additional parking could be added in stages by purchasing lots across Madison Street from the facility. This orientation for the expansion ensures the continued use of the new main entrance for the facility.

When the school relocates the students who live north of the Platt Street viaduct will be bussed from a central location to the new K-12 facility. As a recreation facility, the building could provide for this central location. This use would also provide opportunities for after school activities to flourish, with school children "delivered" right to the door. With this in mind, the parking along Madison Street and East Avenue have been adjusted to accommodate bus loading.

The proposed addition extends directly west from the remaining portion of the original building. This addition houses the gymnasium, administration and "community space". The addition is oriented both north and south. This dual orientation refers to the preference of most to drive to the facility, and the use of the north entrance as the primary. It also makes reference the "civic elevation" along Main Street, and the importance of an articulate public face for the facility.

To the west of the building, space is provided for future expansion of the facility, or outdoor recreation. Space is available for playground or full basketball court. This space could also serve

the groups using the gymnasium as a multi-purpose room by providing more outdoor space.

The site strategy for the project reflects the orthogonal use of the block already exhibited through the existing structures. The placement of the parking behind the building allows for a dramatic “civic elevation” along Main Street. The preservation of the green space between this elevation and Main Street provides an opportunity to enhance the existing “void” in the residential area, provide a more accessible pedestrian entrance to the facility, and a highly organized and dramatic outdoor gathering space.

5.3 Building Design Civic Elevation

The most visible portion of the Montpelier Community Center is the “civic elevation”. This side of the building faces Main Street, and presents the best opportunities for architectural advertisement of the building. This elevation is intended to catch the eye as people pass the site. In addition to catching the eye, the elevation must be legible, both formally and aesthetically.

The initial sketch (fig. 4.6) that resulted in the proposed elevation looked to develop an addition to the building that reflects the organization of the existing building. Between the existing building and the addition, this sketch adds a connection. The connection includes a new accessible entrance, and is shown incorporating super-graphics to advertise the building's use. This element is similar in intention and aesthetics to the connection by Sir Norman Foster at the Joslyn Art Museum.¹

With the demolition of the center of the site, the Main Street elevation is left with a hole. This provides an opportunity for a connector similar to that demonstrated in the early “Limit Sketch” with two jobs: to bridge between and connect the two existing elements, the gymnasium portal and existing 1915 elevation. In order to begin ordering this elevation (especially the connection) two diagrams were developed. The first (fig. 4.10) uses the proportions of the original building to order the addition and connection. The second (fig. 4.11) simplifies this diagram to a progression of certain elements of the 1915 and gymnasium elevations.

5.6 Limit Sketch (for larger images of all limit sketches see appendix 19, page 172)

5.7 1915/Gymnasium

5.8 Sketch

5.9 Sketch

5.10 Diagram 1

5.11 Diagram 2

¹ See *Joslyn Art Museum*, p.112.

Organization

The building is intended as a meeting place for all members of the community in an informal, social setting. In order to provide this place, the building must be planned in such a way that all members of the community enter use the building from the same point or area. This implies a centralized circulation and organization.

This centralized organization should focus on a common meeting space. It should serve as the main circulation area where both visitors and regular users would move from space to space. The circulation of the community through one point could help to encourage face-to-face interactions, which are important for the growth of a stable and healthy community. Additional space should be provided at the periphery of the central circulation space for informal gathering.

In addition to circulation, this space should serve to tie the facility together. It should provide a view of a great deal of the facility and connection to all parts of the program. This connection ensures that all users and visitors will make their way through this space at some point. In order to prevent this space from becoming a checkpoint, administration should be placed in a manner that provides for easy monitoring of the facility, but at the edge.

By providing a varied and flexible program, the community center is intended to draw a wide variety of people from the village and surrounding communities. By providing a central, common space that is used by every person who steps foot in the door, the potential for interactions and thereby *community* is established.

5.12 Community diagram

5.13 Circulation through a common space

5.14 Connection through a single point

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Correspondence

- 1 Cover letter requesting a place on the agenda of the regular meeting of the Village Council of Montpelier, October 01, 2003.
- 2 Cover letter requesting a place on the agenda of the regular meeting of the Board of Education of the Montpelier Exempted Village Schools, October 01, 2003.
- 3 *Brief* from the presentations to the Village Council (October 13, 2003) and the Board of Education (October 14, 2003).
- 4 Meeting Notes from the Village Council Meeting (October 13, 2003) by Susan Kannel.
- 5 Sample letter to the *Special Projects Group* organizations.

Public Meetings

- 6 Public Meeting 1 – Agenda
- 7 Public Meeting 1 – Results
- 8 Public Meeting 2 - Invitation
- 9 Public Meeting 2 – Agenda
- 10 Public Meeting 2 – Results
- 11 Public Meeting 3 – Invitation
- 12 Public Meeting 3 – Presentation

Press Coverage

- 13 Hulbert, Shannon. "Design Plan Proposed for Community Center." *Bryan Times*, Tuesday, October 14, 2003. (front page)
- 14 Miller, Paul A. "New Center Aim of Thesis." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, October 15, 2003. (front page)
- 15 Foust, Courtney. "Building Discussed." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, October 15, 2003.

- 16 Foust, Courtney. "Student's project idea presented." *Bryan Times*, Thursday, October 22, 2003.
- 17 "Public suggests center ideas." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, November 26, 2003. (front page)
- 18 "Meeting brings center closer." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, December 24, 2003. (front page)
- 19 "Center design meeting Feb. 5" *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, January 28, 2004. (front page)
- 20 "Montpelier Community Center ideas discussed." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, February 11, 2004. (front page)
- 21 "Old Building Demolition." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, March 3, 2004.

Design

- 22 Limit Sketches

Fax Cover Letter

To: **Mr John Bitler** Pages: **2** (including cover)
Administrator, Village of Montpelier

Fax: **(419) 485-4947**

Phone: (419) 485-5543

Date: 10/01/03

Re: Agenda Request

Mr Bitler,

Attached is a letter informing the Council of the Village of Montpelier of a project I intend to pursue in the Village of Montpelier. Because the community-at-large will be invited to participate in this project, I felt it only prudent to inform the Village Council and gain its approval.

As stated in the letter, I request a few minutes of the agenda for the meeting of the Village Council on Monday, October 13, 2003. Please inform me as soon as possible if there are any problems with this time.

A hard copy of the letter for dissemination to the members of the Board has been posted today, intended to arrive in Montpelier no later than Friday.

Thank you for your assistance.

Sincerely,

Christopher M Kannel
Graduate Student of Architecture,
University of Cincinnati

MHS, 1998

October 1, 2003

Village of Montpelier Administration
211 N Jonesville St
PO Box 148
Montpelier

Ladies and Gentlemen,

As a graduate student of architecture at the University of Cincinnati, I am working to develop a thesis titled "Architecture by Communities". My thesis focuses on the involvement of a community in the design of space intended for their use.

Specifically, I intend to pursue the design of a community center for the Village of Montpelier. Throughout the design process I intend to invite the community-at-large to several meetings. These meetings would include the discussion of the assets of the community to be included in the project, as well as design criteria and building programming. This project is intended only as an academic exercise, and that fact will be stressed in all invitations.

I request a few moments of the Council's time at the regular meeting on Monday, October 13, 2003. At this meeting, my intentions are to bring more information for the consumption of the Village Administration and gain a measure of approval for the project. I also make myself available to answer any questions that may be deemed relevant at that time.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me via email:

cmkannel@hotmail.com.

Sincerely,

Christopher M Kannel
Graduate Student of Architecture,
University of Cincinnati

MHS, 1998

Fax Cover Letter

To: **Superintendent Tom Lavinder**
Montpelier Exempted Village Schools

Pages: **2** (including cover)

Fax: **(419) 485-4318**

Phone: (419) 485-3676

Date: 10/01/03

Re: Agenda Request

Mr Lavinder,

Attached is a letter informing the Board of Education of a project I intend to pursue in the Village of Montpelier. Because the project may use a portion of property currently owned by the Board of Education, and the community-at-large will be invited to participate in this project, I felt it only prudent to inform the Board and gain its approval.

As stated in the letter, I request a few minutes of the agenda for the meeting of the Board of Education on Tuesday, October 14, 2003. Please inform me as soon as possible if there are any problems with this time.

A hard copy of the letter for dissemination to the members of the Board has been posted today, intended to arrive in Montpelier no later than Friday.

Thank you for your assistance.

Sincerely,

Christopher M Kannel
Graduate Student of Architecture,
University of Cincinnati

MHS, 1998

October 1, 2003

Board of Education
Montpelier Exempted Village Schools
110 N East Ave
Montpelier

Ladies and Gentlemen,

As a graduate student of architecture at the University of Cincinnati, I am working to develop a thesis titled "Architecture by Communities". My thesis focuses on the involvement of a community in the design of space intended for their use.

Specifically, I intend to pursue the design of a community center for the Village of Montpelier, incorporating a portion of the existing high school building. Throughout the design process I intend to invite the community-at-large to several meetings. I understand the Board of Education has intentions for demolishing the high school. However, I believe that the preservation of the historic building is a worthwhile aspiration, and could be a motivating factor for the involvement of the community.

I request a few moments of the Board's time at the regular meeting on Tuesday, October 14, 2003. At this meeting, my intentions are to bring more information for the consumption of the Board of Education and gain a measure of approval for the project. I also make myself available to answer any questions that may be deemed relevant at that time.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me via email:

cmkannel@hotmail.com.

Sincerely,

Christopher M Kannel
Graduate Student of Architecture,
University of Cincinnati

MHS, 1998

Brief

Intentions: This project is an academic exercise with three primary functions:

1. To develop of a methodology for community involvement in design.
2. To design a realistic community center for the Village of Montpelier.
3. To fulfill the requirements of a graduate thesis in architecture.

Briefly, the goal of my thesis is the development and execution of a method in participatory design using “asset-based planning”. Asset-based planning starts new ideas using the existing, positive characteristics of the community. These new ideas are then used to create new environments for the community: economic, social, and physical.

I intend to invite the community of Montpelier to participate in the design process of a facility to compliment the existing service and outreach structure here. The community is defined as anyone living in Montpelier, who is under the jurisdiction of the Village of Montpelier, uses facilities in Montpelier, read publications from the Village, etc. Put another way, there is no limit to who will be invited to participate.

Specifically, I intend to invite several individuals to participate in a focused *Special Project Group* (the building committee). This group is intended to represent the community in miniature, with members representing multiple groups, organizations and the demographics of the community. This group will be asked to make detail-oriented decisions for the design, to be commented on at the public meetings.

Project Description: A Community Center for the Village of Montpelier

The final project will be the result of countless interviews and surveys. These surveys are intended to determine the existing positive aspects of the community, and the spatial (room) requirements needed to compliment them. The public's role is in the generation of ideas for inclusion in the project, as well as critique of the building's overall appearance. The critiques will be gathered at the public meetings, for use by the architect and the *SPG*.

The project will follow the “Methodology” described on page 2, including regular public meetings and even more regular *SPG* meetings. This is an accelerated nine-month schedule, intended to fulfill the University of Cincinnati's graduate requirements. This schedule may also be a benefit for the community because of the regular observation of progress.

At this point, the Community Center for Montpelier is intended as an academic exercise, with only limited aspiration to go beyond the design stages. This fact will be made clear at every meeting, and with every invitation.

Methodology

October

- 13 & 14, meet with Village Council and Board of Education for public announcement/approval
- Begin selection of *Special Project Group*
- Develop methodology for surveying the community

November

- 1-15, Public Meeting to begin the survey process
- Compile survey information, begin schematic design
- Meet with *SPG* 1-2 times – Emphasis: Program/Precedent

December

- Public Meeting to reveal survey results and beginning of design
- Survey reception to community participation
- Meet with *SPG* 2-3 times – Emphasis: Spatial Organization/Uses

January

- Continue Schematic Design
- Meet with *SPG* 3-4 times – Emphasis: Spatial Organization and exterior design

February

- Public Meeting to update and clarify any discrepancies in the design
- Incorporate responses from public meeting
- Meet with *SPG* 3-4 times – Emphasis: Exterior and Site Design

March

- Begin Final Design documentation
- Meet with *SPG* 3-4 times – Emphasis: Approval of progress of design

April

- Finalize Design
- (Last Week) Public Meeting for review of Design – Survey responses

May

- Compile results of Public Review
- Conclusions and completion of written documentation

Meeting Notes

Village Council Meeting, Monday, October 13, 2003, 7:30pm by Susan Kannel

Members in Attendance: Laura Gray, Ric Echler, Delmar Karnes, Kelly Hephner, Steven Yagelski, William Bish, John Bitler, Dean Skiles, Barbara Fisher, James Rockey

Mr Yagelski-town needs a new community center

Mr Echler-would be good for weddings, class reunions.
all we have is the Gillette building, but needs air conditioning
usually end up at exit 2

Mrs Gray-Will you provide ways to pay for it?
The research for this thesis will include some research into funding. There are databases for grants and other funding measures that may apply to this project. The final project will include some references to these resources.

Mr Echler-Will it fit architecturally?
The intention is the design of a facility that is unique to Montpelier, making use of the personality as well as architectural character of the community. Most of the discussion with the general public will focus on this aspect, as a public representation of the community.
-What people want?
The public will be invited to discuss their ideas, their vision, and their preferences for both the design and function of the building.
-How large will it be?
The final building program will be determined from input from the community.

Mr Yagelski-Will this work be done in conjunction with the Revitalization Committee?
The Revitalization Committee will be invited. All of the community will be invited to participate in the public meetings. Ideally, there will be some 5,000 people at each of these meetings to ensure that the community is actively and equally represented.

Mr Echler-How detailed will it be? Heating, Ventilation, etc.
The final project is required by the University of Cincinnati to be a complete building. Ideally, when the process is complete, the work could be handed over to an architect and construction documents could be drawn up. In other words, all the parts of the building will have been considered by the time the process is over.

Mr Yagelski-“I think you know you have the council's support.”
-contact either Ms Hephner or Mr Bitler for a place to hold meetings
-HS students in attendance were encouraged to participate in the process
-asked the press to publish methodology and announcements.
-good luck.

October 17, 2003

Montpelier Area Chamber of Commerce
410 West Main Street
Montpelier

Ladies and Gentlemen,

As a member of the Chamber of Commerce, you know the multitude of benefits that this community has to offer. No one knows better the assets of Montpelier than its residents, especially those involved with its day-to-day maintenance. It is for this reason that I invite the residents of Montpelier to assist in an academic project for its improvement. As a graduate student of architecture, I am working on a thesis titled "Architecture for Communities". My thesis focuses on the design of a community center for the Village of Montpelier.

I am inviting the community-at-large to participate in the design process, beginning with a public meeting on Thursday, November 13, 2003. This meeting will be held in the auditorium of Montpelier High School at 7:30pm.

Your role in this process will help to make it a truly productive endeavor, not only for my thesis, but for the community as a whole. If you choose to help, you will serve as one of many consultants in what characteristics of Montpelier can be implemented into this building program. *It is important for you to know that this project is purely academic, in that no building is necessarily going to be built.* Please encourage your family and friends to attend this event.

I also request a volunteer from the Chamber of Commerce to serve on a *Special Project Group*, a small committee representing the community in detail-oriented design issues. I am willing to make myself available for an in-person presentation of this element to a meeting of the Chamber, if deemed appropriate.

I thank you for your involvement in the community of Montpelier, and your help in this endeavor. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me via email or phone:

cmkannel@hotmail.com or 513.708.1963

Sincerely,

Christopher M Kannel
Graduate Student of Architecture,
University of Cincinnati

MHS, 1998

Outline

- 1.0 To increase awareness in the public of the intentions of the project.
- 2.0 To understand how the community sees itself.
- 3.0 To develop a program that reflects the wishes and interests of the community.

1.0 Community Assets (25-30 minutes)

Goal: To determine what unique potential the community sees in itself; what positive aspects should be considered in designing a "hub" for the community.¹ These assets will be used immediately in phase 3.0, and will help in developing the program for the building by providing the elements of the community the public see as the most important.

Materials: Paper and easel for recording and displaying the characteristics mentioned by the participants.

Organization: Participants will be seated in the gallery, facing the stage.

Rules: Every comment is relevant and not up for discussion. Participants will be asked to wait for their turn to speak, and to limit their comments to a few words. Participants may present ideas as often as they are called on.

1.1 What aspects are unique about Montpelier?

What factors make Montpelier unique in the county, in the nation?

- This question is intended to invoke ideas about the history, character, and spirit of the community.
- The participants need to look to their community as a singular place in the fabric of the world. These unique characteristics will help the project connect with the community. This will prevent the "Anywhere, USA" site that is common to many community centers.

1.2 What makes Montpelier a great place to live?

What elements of the community enhance the experience of living in a small town?

- This question is intended to solicit the passive assets of the town. These are the physical and spatial characteristics that may be typical, even stereotypical, of a small town, but those that the participants feel are important for the living conditions in Montpelier.
- These are important for considering what physical and spatial elements should be included in the new facility. These will also be helpful for phase 3.0, as a starting point for important physical and spatial attributes.

1.3 What unique assets does Montpelier have to offer?

What are the elements that benefit the community?

- This question is intended to draw out the benefits that are offered in the community. These may include services, organizations, clubs, etc that should be considered when planning the facility.
- The benefits the community has to offer could dictate how the facility will be used, when it will be open, who will use it, and what spaces will be needed. The community knows what it has to offer, and what aspects are more or less important. This will help to prevent the inclusion of a less important aspect over one that is more important simply by oversight.

Objective: In order to better understand how the community sees itself, we need to have them tell us. Kretzman and McKnight argue that the road to community improvement should start "with what is present in the community, the capacities of its residents and workers."² However, in order to find these capacities/assets, the community should be interviewed. Knowing what the important elements of the community are will not only help the designer (me) to make the design most appropriate, it also demonstrates to the community what is really worth saving.

¹ Adapted from Kretzmann, John P and John L McKnight. (1993) *Building Communities from the Inside Out: A Path Toward Finding and Mobilizing a Community's Assets*. Chicago: ACTA Publications.

² Ibid. p 9.

- "Strong communities are basically places where the capacities of local residents are identified, valued, and used."³ So while this project may or may not be realized in any form, to have begun the process of identifying these capacities can be highly valuable.

2.0 Public Awareness (10-15 minutes)

Goal: To demonstrate the need for a re-centering of the community of Montpelier.

Materials: Powerpoint presentation.

Organization: This presentation comes after the discussion of assets for several reasons:

1. The positive aspects that could be preserved by a new community center should be discussed and presented by the participants. To discuss these before the open forum may influence the discussion toward what I have already talked about. Additionally, my presentation can draw on these principles.
2. The negative aspects that I intend to discuss could influence the discussion as well. The participants should start the meeting on a positive note, digging into the great opportunities that are afforded them in Montpelier. Once they recognize these, they should be shown how these great opportunities are being threatened.
3. This presentation could be an effective transition from the nebulous concept phase ("Awareness") to the idea phase ("Perception").⁴ After a discussion about what the community has to offer, it is important to give the reason for discussing what a place that preserves these qualities should be like (phase 3.0).

2.1 Sprawl.

2.1.1. Sprawl is a national epidemic that is affecting most all major cities, and even Montpelier.

- Industry moved out of downtown (not necessarily bad)
- Commercial enterprises moved out of downtown
- The school moved to the outskirts of town

2.1.2. The community's center is being degraded.

- Many vacant buildings on Main Street

2.2 A project needs to be developed to retain the orientation of the community toward its unique qualities, origin and history.

Objective: This presentation is intended to give the participants something to talk about during the break. After discussing what is good about the community and how it is being threatened, the participants will hopefully be energized to develop solutions to that threat. This also focuses the ideas toward problem solving, rather than idle discussion which is often perceived as wasteful.

Break (5-10 minutes)

3.0 "Patterns/Concepts" (25-30 minutes)

Goal: To determine the character of space the community desires in a facility for their use.⁵ Using the characteristics discussed in phase 1.0, the group exercises will provide the opportunity for participants to draw and list the qualities of spaces, relationships between spaces, and relative

³ Ibid. p 13.

⁴ Sanoff, Henry. (2000) *Community Participation Methods in Design and Planning*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. pp 10-11. Sanoff describes the categories of factors that influence the participation process. *Awareness* "involves discovering or rediscovering the realities of a given environment or situation" so that everyone is on the same page. *Perception* "entails going from awareness of a situation to understanding it an its...ramifications". These are followed by *Decision Making* and *Implementation*. These are adapted from J. Burns.

⁵ This phase of the meeting was developed based on "Workshop #1" from: Oberdorfer, Jeff. "Community participation in the design of the Boulder Creek Branch Library." in Sanoff, Henry, ed. (1990) *Participatory Design: Theory & Techniques*. Raleigh, NC: Henry Sanoff. pp 110-119.

sizes as they deem important. This will assist in the design of the program as well as the layout of the building.

Materials: Large sheets of paper for each group, markers (Crayola 6-pack), assets from phase 2.0.

Organization: Participants will be asked to form groups of 6 or 7. These groups will be arranged at tables and provided the materials mentioned above.

Rules: All ideas are relevant, potentially helpful, and should be represented based on importance and connection.

3.1 Participants should imagine the ideal community center. What sorts of elements should this place contain, and how are they connected?

- Everyone has an idea of what goes into a community center. Most of the time we are limited by budget, site, etc. This portion will allow the participants to dream, and be heard. Here, they have the opportunity to bring all of their ideas to the table, put them on paper, and discuss them with their peers.

3.2 What kinds of places could be included to house/represent/enhance the positive aspects discussed in phase 2.0? How should they feel?

- As the positive aspects of the community, these should be found in a place intended for community use. The participants should be encouraged to decide what aspects would be important for THEIR community center, and how to include them.

3.3 Discussion: After 25-30 minutes of drawing, each group will be asked to present their ideas to the entire gathering.

- Each group should pick a spokesperson and take a minute or two to describe what they drew/listed, and why.

Objective: In allowing the participants to exhibit their ideas, this exercise allows for both a free-flow of ideas and the full breadth of intentions across the community. Two objectives are intended:

1. The participants will feel that their ideas have been heard. Participants will hopefully feel as if they have participated directly in the development of the basic principles of the design.
2. The design criteria can be drawn directly from these descriptions.⁶

4.0 Introduction of site (5-10 minutes)

Goal: To demonstrate the potential for a new community center at the existing high school building.

Materials: Powerpoint presentation, site model.

4.1 Introduction of the high school as the possible site for a new community center.

4.2 Show the possible configuration of the addition on the site.

Objective: This brief presentation is intended to spark conversation among the participants as to the potential for the site, its feasibility, and whether they like the idea. As the intention has been published in the papers, it is also important to publicly defend the idea at the initial stages of the project. With the physical site model at the event, it will allow for detailed conversations after the meeting's conclusion.

⁶ Ibid. p 112. Oberdorfer describes a similar step intended "to begin establishing the feeling-or ambience-of the library, by defining small parts, scaled to the individual library user. Parts which participants valued as being essential to the success of *their* [project]."

Summary: The meeting started at 7:30pm, with 13 people (unrelated to me) in attendance. We finished at 8:30pm, with the results listed below. While the turnout was slightly disappointing, the comments and ideas gleaned from the participants will be extremely helpful in developing the program and designing the facility. These ideas also helped to reinforce or dispel some of my intuitive responses to the project.

The results of the survey filled out by the participants indicate that the discussion was worthwhile. All of the participants gave the meeting high marks for meaningful results, the possibilities of the project, and willingness for continued involvement.

1.0 Community Assets

Objective: In order to better understand how the community sees itself, we need to have them tell us.

Kretzman and McKnight argue that the road to community improvement should start “with what is present in the community, the capacities of its residents and workers.”⁷ However, in order to find these capacities/assets, the community should be interviewed. Knowing what the important elements of the community are will not only help the designer (me) to make the design most appropriate, it also demonstrates to the community what is really worth saving.

- “Strong communities are basically places where the capacities of local residents are identified, valued, and used.”⁸ So while this project may or may not be realized in any form, to have begun the process of identifying these capacities can be highly valuable.

Summary: The discussion around this topic focused primarily on question 1.1. Montpelier’s unique characteristics were of primary concern, although there was some discussion about quality of life issues. The items listed by the group follows:

- best water (in the world, according to a test...source tbd)
- supportive and Friendly (referring to the people living in the community)
- fairgrounds (County) – brings people to the community
- Williams County Historical Society Museum
- intact downtown
- volunteerism (referring to the people living in the community)
- close to (the Ohio) Turnpike
- large variety of churches
- good parks
- good education system
- good zoning/plan for the future
- good village employees
- good EMS and hospital
- good library
- (people) keep an eye out for each other
- (there are people who have) dreams for a brighter future
- the community is involved in education
- excellent non-profit organizations and service clubs

⁷ Ibid. p 9.

⁸ Ibid. p 13.

Commentary: While the discussion was positive, I feel the group had difficulty getting to the heart of the issue. While I wanted them to think critically about the community, they were thinking about the “warm-fuzzy” issues that gloss over what the community lacks. I feel the participants had difficulty finding the relevance of the discussion of assets when they were there to discuss a community center. This connection should have been more directly stated, and should have been made clearer in through the questions asked.

In the end, the discussion was helpful for both the participants and me. On a scale of 0-9 (not at all to absolutely meaningful), the participants rated the meeting at an average of 8.4. Each of the items listed are important for understanding how the community sees itself. This will help the in the programming and future outreach to the community.

Improvements: In order to better serve the objectives of the phase, the objectives should have been made clearer to the participants. While a level of ambiguity was necessary to prevent inadvertently influencing the discussion, the participants were unsure of the intent of the exercise. I believe this was to the detriment of the discussion.

In addition, the discussion could have included the needs or deficiencies of the community. In talking only about the positive, the group may have glossed over some of the most important issues in the community. In this way, some of the later discussions may have been limited by this lack of full disclosure. It is unclear how much, if any, the discussion was limited. It would be interesting to try discussing both and looking at the results.

3.0 “Patterns/Concepts”

Objective: In allowing the participants to exhibit their ideas, this exercise allows for both a free-flow of ideas and the full breadth of intentions across the community. Two objectives are intended:

1. The participants will feel that their ideas have been heard. Participants will hopefully feel as if they have participated directly in the development of the basic principles of the design.
2. The design criteria can be drawn directly from these descriptions.⁹

Summary: The patterns/concepts phase seemed to be most beneficial for the participants, and will be most helpful for me. The participants were divided into three groups, each with their own paper and markers. The discussion among the groups was lively, with two of the groups using most all of the page. All of the groups seemed hesitant to draw, but were more than willing to write down what they discussed, and what was deemed important to them. The responses varied between space types, activity types, and qualities that should be incorporated. Some were duplicated, so the list below represents all of the responses:

Space Types

- Kitchen (many uses)
- Raised Space
- Photogenic Areas
- Storage area for tables, chairs
- Adequate restrooms

⁹ Ibid, p 112. Oberdorfer describes a similar step intended “to begin establishing the feeling-or ambience-of the library, by defining small parts, scaled to the individual library user. Parts which participants valued as being essential to the success of *their* [project].”

- Smaller meeting rooms
- Computer Area
- Game room – pool tables, darts, indoor pool
- Daycare
- Teen Hangout
- Playground area
- Study/Reading area
- Lobby with a lounge
- Aerobics classroom

Activity Types

- Bean Days Activities (Community's summer festival)
- Banquets
- Graduation/Birthday Party area
- Art Exhibits
- Reverse Raffle
- Family Reunions
- Class Reunions
- Wedding Receptions
- Recreational Area
- Halloween Judging, Party
- Christmas Party
- Music/Arts
- Village Annual Banquet

Qualities

- Parking
- Handicap Accessible
- Versatile Design
- Sound System
- Well Landscaped
- Acoustics
- Fountain
- Good Location
- "A draw of such beauty that others from the surrounding community come use this facility"
- Historic Aspect – Vintage – looks like Montpelier
- A/C
- Occupancy 300-500
- High ceilings
- Large double doors for vehicles
- Comfortable – not like big city
- Not an industrial look

Questions

- Who does it belong to?
- Who pays insurance?
- Who manages?
- Who cleans? –trash removal-
- What equipment is furnished?
- Cost of rental?

Commentary: Some comments after the meeting indicated that there was difficulty relating this phase to phase 1.0. It seemed that the participants had difficulty understanding the intention of enhancing what is already good about the community through the building. Instead, they focused on question 3.1, the ideal community center. In this case, they focused mostly on a single space for community use: a banquet-type hall. Their ideas focused mainly on what these spaces would be like, what they would include, and what they would be used for.

The elements that the participants felt were important serve to reinforce some of the original intentions of the project. They also bring a few new ideas to the project. For instance, "large double doors for vehicles" provides an alternative pattern in terms of flexibility. The space that this group imagined could be used for more than just parties. It could be used as an exhibition hall as well. This pattern could bring a new approach to the use, arrangement, orientation and materiality of a space. "Historic aspect-vintage-looks like Montpelier" emphasizes the importance for the participants of the maintenance of the community's architectural character. This new building should fit neatly into the context of the community.

Conclusion: While some of the results were disappointing, the information that was gathered was extremely encouraging. There is much room for improvement.

For better attendance at the next meeting, the following changes will be implemented:

- increased number and frequency of invitations – groups should be reminded of the opportunity for participation, and informed of the results of PM 1.
- improved communication with the local newspaper – more information will be forwarded to the paper, especially as the date for the next meeting draws near.

For improved discussion in the next meeting, the following changes will be implemented:

- more detailed explanation of the objectives of the exercises – give the participants a clear understanding of why they are being asked to do what they are doing, and what the result will be.
- more group activities, those that allow small groups to solve problems rather than group discussion – participants seemed hesitant to speak publicly, but were much more willing to talk around a table, or explain their group's stance on an issue.

Please plan to attend

Public Meeting 2 for the
Montpelier Community Center

Thurs, December 11
7:30pm
at MHS

We will discuss what the proposed Center should include, look like, and how it will feel. The meeting will include a recap of the first Public Meeting.

Tell your family and friends!

Questions? contact Chris Kannel

cmkannel@hotmail.com
513.708.1963

<http://said.uc.edu/students/kannelc>

RESIDENT OF MONTEPELIER
ADDRESS
MONTEPELIER OH 43543

Outline

- 1.0 Recount the discussion of the first public meeting.
- 2.0 Discuss the program elements that came out of the first public meeting.
- 3.0 Implement the program into a site strategy.

1.0 Recount the discussion of the first public meeting (10-15 minutes)

Goal: To evaluate the goals and intentions outlined by the participants at the first public meeting and make them relevant to the project.

1.1 Community Assets

- 1.1.1. The three most relevant assets that were mentioned were:

Fairgrounds (County)

Intact downtown

Excellent non-profit and service clubs

These assets demonstrate the high potential areas that make the community unique, and should be included in the building and site strategies that develop.

- 1.1.2. The County Fairgrounds and the Downtown represent divergent issues in the community.

- 1.1.2.1. The Fairgrounds represents the destination of people coming from all over Williams County, and sometimes further. While hundreds (perhaps thousands) of visitors come to the Fair, very little benefit is matched to the community.

- 1.1.2.2. The Downtown is the place where residents of Montpelier do (consistently less and less) of their business. While the buildings are still there, nearly half are vacant.

While these seem like different parts of the community, they actually represent two major nodes along Main Street. Separated by only five blocks, they present a unique datum by which the community is represented. These nodes represent one major reason people come to Montpelier and the place that could be developed to keep them coming back. Nearly at the midpoint of this datum is the site selected for the Montpelier Community Center, the site of Montpelier High School. This site presents a unique opportunity to connect the County Fairgrounds with the Historic Downtown of Montpelier, a connection which could help to stimulate the intended growth of the downtown.

This facility should also include the needs of the non-profit and service groups that are an important part of the community. They should be considered a major user group.

1.2 Patterns/Concepts

- 1.2.1. Space types discussed revealed the need for a large space to facilitate the activity types discussed below. This space is to be accented by lounge spaces both for major events, and for general use. These accessory spaces could be used for studying and tutoring after school to relieve the burden on the public library.

- 1.2.2. Activity types included:

Bean Days Activities	Wedding Receptions
Banquets	Recreational Area
Graduation/Birthday Party area	Halloween Judging, Party
Art Exhibits	Christmas Party
Reverse Raffle	Music/Arts
Family Reunions	Village Annual Banquet
Class Reunions	

- 1.2.3. Qualities that the facility should exhibit made it clear that the space needs to be one that encourages its use by people outside the community as well residents of Montpelier. This space is to be versatile, "beautiful" and in a good location.

2.0 Site and Program (20-25 minutes)

Goal: To exhibit the space types and qualities visually, and demonstrate the relationships necessary between them.

Materials: Powerpoint presentation.

2.1 From the discussion of space types that came from Public Meeting 1, the building program included:

- Lobby
- Great Hall/Banquet Hall
- Exterior Space
- Lounge
- Kitchen
- Kitchen Storage
- Public Restrooms
- Meeting/Conference/Activity Room
- Classrooms
- Aerobics/Dance Space
- Game Room

2.2 In addition to these basic spaces, several were necessary to add for the maintenance and upkeep of the facility:

- Storage of Audiovisual equipment
- Administration spaces
- Custodial and Mechanical spaces

2.3 A final series of additions to the program came as a result of precedent investigations. These spaces would increase the variety of activities offered by the facility and its potential draw from within and from outside the community:

- Gymnasium
- Locker/Changing/Restrooms

Break (5-10 minutes)

3.0 Site and Program II (25-30 minutes)

Goal: To encourage a participant developed site and building strategy for the Montpelier Community Center.

Materials: Large sheets of paper for each group, markers (Crayola 6-pack), program elements from phase 2.0, handout.

Organization: Participants will be asked to form groups of 6 or 7. These groups will be arranged at tables and provided the materials mentioned above.

Rules: All ideas are relevant, potentially helpful, and should be represented based on importance and connection.

3.1 Participants are to determine the important relationships between the major elements of the building.

3.1.1. Based on those described in the Handout, which are the major spaces?

3.1.2. How should these spaces relate? Should they be connected, be separate?

3.1.3. What secondary spaces should be related to them?

3.1.4. How should they relate to the entrance?

These relationships will help the participants discover the necessary relationships between spaces. These relationships drive the planning of a building by setting specific criteria for where specific spaces need to.

3.2 Participants should then determine their relationship to the site?

3.2.1. Which spaces desire views?

3.2.2. Which views are important?

Views are extremely important when planning spaces that desire natural light. Windows should be placed to maximize specific and desirable views. Part of this process is determining what the desirable and undesirable views are, and how they can be captured.

3.3 Participants should finally place the building on the site?

3.3.1. What side should be the front?

3.3.2. Where should parking be located?

3.3.3. What should be green, and what should be building?

When the relationships and views are determined, the building should be placed on the site to accomplish all of these criteria. This final step should produce a site plan that incorporates the necessary relationships between spaces and then with the site that the groups developed.

Objective: By providing all the tools necessary for a site strategy, two objectives are intended:

1. With a first hand working knowledge of the community and its potential, the participants may have a unique insight into the true potential for the site. Using this potential, the groups may develop uniquely helpful strategies that could be implemented in the design of a new facility.
2. Having worked through some of the problems involved in the development of a site strategy, the participants should have a better understanding of the consequences of design and planning decisions. With this understanding, they may be more likely to accept one that both uses their intentions and introduces some new intentions.

4.0 Discussion (5-10 minutes)

Goal: To communicate ideas and encourage a level of understanding between groups.

4.1 Groups will be asked to share the ideas developed for their site strategy.

4.2 The other groups will be asked to respond to the ideas presented.

Objective: While working together, each group will have made certain assumptions and dismissed certain ideas about the site and building. In this portion of the meeting, each group will see how some one else treated the site. The results may be similar, or they may be divergent. In any case, every group will certainly have convincing arguments for their plans, some that may not have been considered by another group. This sense of options should give the participants a better understanding of the decisions made and dismissed during the design process. This will hopefully encourage more thoughtful questions about intent and development at the next public meeting.

Summary: The meeting began at 7:30pm in the auditorium of Montpelier High School. Ten (mostly new) people attended the meeting. Results from the survey were mixed with the greatest interest in the group work. Most felt that the interaction of the participants in the second half of the workshop produced good results.

The meeting lasted until 9:15pm, with more time allowed for phase 3.0.

1.0 Recount the discussion of the first public meeting (10-15 minutes)

Goal: To evaluate the goals and intentions outlined by the participants at the first public meeting and make them relevant to the project.

1.1 Community Assets

1.2 Patterns/Concepts

Commentary: It was necessary to describe the results of the first meeting to relate the new-found importance of the proposed site. This importance drove a good part of the conversation at the break and after the meeting, which was a happy coincidence. This new facet of the project was important to make the project economically and socially relevant to the participants and the community as a whole.

Improvements: While the presentation was short, an opportunity for comments or questions from the participants would have been helpful. Most of those in attendance had not participated in Public Meeting 1, and so had little idea what had happened. The use of a wireless mouse for better slide changes or other methods to improve eye contact with the participants would also have been beneficial to convey the ideas better.

2.0 Site and Program (20-25 minutes)

Goal: To exhibit the space types and qualities visually, and demonstrate the relationships necessary between them.

2.1 From the discussion of space types that came from Public Meeting 1

2.2 In addition to these basic spaces, several were necessary to add for the maintenance and upkeep of the facility

2.3 A final series of additions to the program came as a result of precedent investigations.

Commentary: Presentation was too long without much relevance. While it was important to describe the spaces that were intended, and how they were intended to feel, it was more important to describe how those spaces were come to, how the sizes would be determined, etc.

Improvements: This presentation would have benefited from a handout. Slides flashing by quickly made for a difficult time following what was being discussed. The jump from Public Meeting 1 to the program should have been discussed in greater detail to prevent later additions by the participants. The program should have been discussed as a well-considered and thorough document, not to be added to or subtracted from.

In the future, do not show photos of elements that are not explicitly intended for the project.

3.0 Site and Program II (25-30 minutes)

Goal: To encourage a participant developed site and building strategy for the Montpelier Community Center.

3.1 Participants are to determine the important relationships between the major elements of the building.

3.2 Participants should then determine their relationship to the site?

3.3 Participants should finally place the building on the site?

Objective: By providing all the tools necessary for a site strategy, two objectives are intended:

1. With a first hand working knowledge of the community and its potential, the participants may have a unique insight into the true potential for the site. Using this potential, the groups may develop uniquely helpful strategies that could be implemented in the design of a new facility.
2. Having worked through some of the problems involved in the development of a site strategy, the participants should have a better understanding of the consequences of design and planning decisions. With this understanding, they may be more likely to accept one that both uses their intentions and introduces some new intentions.

Commentary: The demolition group took too much time deciding whether or not to demolish the whole existing building. This resulted in too little time spent on the plan of a new building. One comment from a participant: "this is why we don't design by committee" came from this group.

The preservation group took too much liberty in adding space and function that is not intended for the building. These took more space than allotted.

Improvements: More structure should have been set for this portion of the meeting. A time limit should have been placed on the decision to keep or not to keep the existing building. While consensus should be reached over taking a vote, the meeting needs to end on time.

More explicit instructions on the use of the program should be given to prevent adding or taking away. In order to make an accurate comparison between strategies, they need to be similar in size, type, etc.

4.0 Discussion (5-10 minutes)

Goal: To communicate ideas and encourage a level of understanding between groups.

4.1 Groups will be asked to share the ideas developed for their site strategy.

4.2 The other groups will be asked to respond to the ideas presented.

Objective: While working together, each group will have made certain assumptions and dismissed certain ideas about the site and building. In this portion of the meeting, each group will see how some one else treated the site. The results may be similar, or they may be divergent. In any case, every group will certainly have convincing arguments for their plans, some that may not have been considered by another group. This sense of options should give the participants a better understanding of the decisions made and dismissed during the design process. This will hopefully encourage more thoughtful questions about intent and development at the next public meeting.

Commentary: The discrepancies between the two strategies resulted in a great deal of interest from either group. An encouraging result of this discussion was the willingness of each group to concede to some of the divergent ideas that the other group came up

with. While the premise of saving the existing building was not respected by both groups, the general orientation of the drawings was the same.

Improvements: None to speak of. The discussion portion went very well.

Please plan to attend

Public Meeting 3 for the
Montpelier Community Center
will be held

Thurs, February 5
7:30pm at MHS

See a proposed design: sketches, drawings, and models. See the potential of the high school, how it could impact the neighborhood, and how it could help our community. Have a say in how the building should look from here.

Questions? contact Chris Kannel

cmkannel@hotmail.com
513.708.1963

<http://said.uc.edu/students/kannelc>

RESIDENT OF MONTEPELIER
ADDRESS
MONTEPELIER OH 43543

Schematic Design - In Progress Work

Elevation 1

Connection 1

Connection 2

Connection 3

Elevation 2

Elevation 3

Elevation 4

Proposed Main Street (South) Elevation

Proposed Madison Street (North) Elevation

Proposed Ground Floor Plan

Proposed Elevations, Ground Floor Plan, and Elevation Studies

Chris Kannel, Graduate Student of Architecture
University of Cincinnati

Architecture for a Community
Master of Architecture Thesis

Montpelier Community Center

A

Schematic Design - In Progress Work

Proposed Second Floor Plan

Proposed Third Floor Plan

Proposed Second and Third Floor Plans

Chris Kannel, Graduate Student of Architecture
University of Cincinnati

Architecture for a Community
Master of Architecture Thesis

Montpelier Community Center

B

Schematic Design - In Progress Work

02/20/04

Proposed Site Plan

Joslyn Art Museum Expansion (1994)
Omaha, Nebraska
Sir Norman Foster and Partners

Neighborhood Center (1999)
Copenhagen, Denmark
Dorte Mandrup Arkitekter Aps

Coryville Recreation Center (1999)
Cincinnati, OH
Speer and Speer

Proposed Site Plan and Building Precedents

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C

Montpelier Village Council

Design plan proposed for community center

By SHANNAN HULBERT
Times Wire Editor

MONTPELIER — If Montpelier were to have a new community center, what should it look like? What should it include?

Chris Kannel, a 1998 graduate of Montpelier High School and a current graduate student in architecture at the University of Cincinnati, addressed Montpelier Village Council Monday regarding the design and development of a new community center for the village. The project is for Mr. Kannel's masters thesis.

Mr. Kannel invited the community to participate in the design process of a facility to compliment the existing services and outreach structure in the village.

Specifically, Mr. Kannel is seeking volunteers to be part of a focused Special Project Group to represent the community in miniature. The group will be asked to make detail-oriented decisions for the design, to be commented on at public meetings.

Mr. Kannel's project is set on an accelerated nine-month

(Please see **DESIGN** on Page 2)

Design

schedule to fulfill his graduate requirements. The community center project is, at this point, intended only as an academic exercise, with only limited aspiration to go beyond the design stages. However, Mr. Kannel noted his thesis will be a complete building design in every way, and theoretically could be used as the basis for a community facility.

Council gave wholehearted approval to the project.

Those residents interested in

being part of the Special Project Group will may contact Mr. Kannel at cmkannel@hotmail.com — note *Montpelier Community Center project* or *Special Project Group* in the subject line.

The SPG will meet multiple times November through March, with meetings emphasizing: program/precedent; spatial organization/uses; spatial organization and exterior design; exterior and site design; and approval of progress of design.

Public meetings for the project will be held in November, December, February and April, and the project will be completed in May.

Hulbert, Shannon. "Design Plan Proposed for Community Center." *Bryan Times*, Tuesday, October 14, 2003.

Front page article (from the county's only daily newspaper) detailing the meeting with the Montpelier Village Council.

New center aim of thesis

A Montpelier native's college thesis may result in a new center of activity in the village.

At Monday's regular meeting,

By Paul A. Miller
LE Managing Editor

the village council heard a presentation on the master's thesis of Chris Kannel, architecture graduate student at the University of Cincinnati, and a 1998 grad of Montpelier High School.

Kannel's project will be the development and design of a community center for the village. The

process will include public meetings, citizen involvement and a specific design which will answer the needs expressed by the community. A monthly agenda of meetings and progress markers (see Agenda, page 4) culminates in a public meeting to review the design in April 2004, followed by a compilation of that citizen input and written conclusions.

Several council members noted the agenda is ambitious.

"The schedule may seem to be condensed, but that's so I can grad-

uate in June," Kannel explained, drawing the laughter of all.

Kannel's thesis involves development of the center up to final design only. Village leaders expressed hope that once designed, the project might become a reality with enough public support.

"We have needed a community center for a long time," said Mayor Steve Yagelski. Council members also responded positively to the proposal.

See THESIS on page 2

Thesis

Continued from front

"I think you can tell you've got the council's support, 100 percent," the mayor assured Kannel. "What I want is to urge the citizens to get in contact, get involved in this very worthwhile project."

Kannel thanked council for the support. The selection of a Special Project Group to study community needs will begin immediately. Those wishing to get involved should contact Kannel by e-mail, cmkannel@hotmail.com, or City Hall, 419-485-5543. The first public meeting will be held in early November.

Miller, Paul A. "New Center Aim of Thesis." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, October 15, 2003.

Front page article (from the community's weekly newspaper) detailing the meeting with the Village Council

Building discussed

Architecture graduate student Christopher Kannel presented his idea for a community center at Tuesday's

By Courtney Foust
LE Staff Writer

meeting of the Montpelier Exempted Village Board of Education. (See also council story above.)

Kannel's ideas for the center are part of his master's thesis at the University of Cincinnati. Montpelier High School would serve as the site of his center. He shared illustrations and stated that he wanted to share the details with the board personally.

"So far my faculty are the only people I have discussed this with," the Montpelier High School graduate said. "They are very enthusiastic about my idea and think it works very well in the community structure."

"The high school is an architectural landmark," he said. "I chose this building because of its architectural and psychological centrality in the community."

However, Kannel added that his "realistic building design" is not intended as a real project.

"My pledge is to make clear that this is only an academic exercise," Kannel said.

"I don't intend for this to be built. If it was, it would be really neat. But that is not part of the project."

Foust, Courtney. "Building Discussed." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, October 15, 2003.

Front page article (from the community's weekly newspaper)

Montpelier school board

Student's project idea presented

By **COURTNEY FOUST**
Leader Enterprise

MONTPELIER — Architecture graduate student Christopher Kannel presented his idea for a community center at the Oct. 14 meeting of the Montpelier Exempted Village Board of Education.

Kannel's ideas for the center are part of his master's thesis at the University of Cincinnati. Montpelier High School would serve as the site of his center.

"My pledge is to make clear that this is only an academic exercise," Kannel said. "I don't intend for this to be built."

Foust, Courtney. "Student's project idea presented." *Bryan Times, Thursday, October 22, 2003.*

Article from page 3

Public suggests center ideas

According to a report from the design researcher, the first meeting to consider the need for a community center in Montpelier was quite successful.

Chris Kannel, a Montpelier native and University of Cincinnati student working on a graduate project in architecture, is working through a public meeting and design process which is to culminate in plans for a community center for the village, designed to meet the expressed needs of the public.

At the first meeting, held November 13, 13 residents attended to offer their input. The commu-

nity's present assets were listed first, including: a supportive and friendly population, the Williams County Historical Society Museum, an intact downtown, volunteerism of residents, the large variety of churches, good parks, a good education system and good zoning and plans for the future.

Then discussion turned to the patterns and concepts suggested for the community center. Among the ideas were: Space Types - kitchen, raised space, photogenic areas, storage area for tables, chairs, adequate restrooms, smaller meeting rooms and a computer area; Activity

Types - Bean Days activities, banquets, graduation/birthday party area, art exhibits, reverse raffle and family reunions; Qualities - parking, handicap accessible, versatile design, sound system, well landscaped, acoustics and a fountain.

In his report, Kannel noted the participants wished to see the building maintain the community's historic architectural character.

The agenda for the December 11 meeting will include building layout on the site and specific design elements. All interested members of the community are encouraged to attend.

"Public suggests center ideas." The Leader Enterprise, Wednesday, November 26, 2003.

Front page article describing the results of Public Meeting 1.

Meeting brings center closer

The second public meeting on the Montpelier Community Center proposal was held December 11.

Ten residents shared their thoughts and discussed details of the proposed building, based on input from the initial public meet-

ing held in November.

Among the items which are to be included in the proposal are: a great hall, a lounge, a kitchen, a meeting/conference/activity room, classrooms, a gymnasium, locker rooms, aerobics/dance space, a

game room, administration, a loading dock and parking.

Sketches were made, based on the Montpelier High School facility, with options to use a portion of that building or start anew.

The design phase will now begin, with Chris Kannel developing design drawings, sketches and models.

Kannel, a Montpelier native, is a graduate student in architecture at the University of Cincinnati.

The intention of his project is to develop a community center based on public input. Once the design is completed, residents can choose whether to move forward with the concept.

"Meeting brings center closer." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, December 24, 2003.

Front page article detailing the results of Public Meeting 2.

Center design meeting Feb. 5

The next public meeting for the Montpelier Community Center will be held Thursday, Feb. 5 at 7:30 p.m. at the Montpelier High School.

Those attending will see a proposed design, sketches, drawings, and models. The potential of the high school, and how it could impact the neighborhood and help the community will be presented and discussed.

The development of a Montpelier Community Center is the graduate project of Chris Kannel, an architecture student at the University of Cincinnati.

While no funding has yet been designated for the community center, Kannel's project aims to develop a comprehensive study of the community's needs and complete the design for a center which would meet those needs. Residents, community groups and village government will then have the opportunity to study the work and choose whether to move forward on the project.

If you have questions, contact Chris Kannel at cmkannel@hotmail.com or call 513-708-1963.

"Center design meeting Feb. 5." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, January 28, 2004.

Front page announcement of Public Meeting 3.

Montpelier Community Center ideas discussed

Courtney Foust/Leader Enterprise

At last Thursday's public meeting, Chris Kannel, a graduate student in architecture at the University of Cincinnati, uses a model of the Montpelier High School to show what he has developed for a community center. Public input has helped Mr. Kannel put together the proposal, which will be discussed further at future meetings.

"Montpelier Community Center ideas discussed." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, February 11, 2004.

Front page photo from Public Meeting 3.

Speaking of Montpelier Schools

By Tom Lavinder, Superintendent
Montpelier Exempted Village Schools

Old Building Demolition

We are getting closer to the beginning of our new school construction process. Over the next few weeks we will begin to see activity at the site and a structure will begin to emerge before our eyes. This will be very exciting for all of us as we anticipate the opening of this wonderful structure.

Occasionally we will be asked questions about the plans for one current buildings once the new school is occupied. This is a question we have discussed at several public forums and public monthly board of education meetings. It should be noted that the school board has already passed resolutions noted in the meeting minutes to take the following action:

Montpelier High School: Demolition.

Storrer Elementary School: Demolition.

Superior Middle School:
Demolition of the pre-1979
structure only.

The demolition of these olden buildings is already a part of the overall building project and will not require additional local funds. As is the case with the building construction, the demolition is funded with 80% state funds and 20% local funds already voted in our local bond issue approved November, 2002.

If anyone has questions about the demolition of the old buildings which will not occur until the spring of 2006, please contact my office at 419-485-3676, or mntplr_s@nwoca.org.

"Old Building Demolition." *The Leader Enterprise*, Wednesday, March 3, 2004.

Open letter from the Superintendent of the Montpelier Exempted Village Schools. The letter reasserts the will of the Board of Education to tear down the existing school buildings when the new K-12 complex is complete.

Three sketches recommended by Prof. Niland at my Fall Quarter review. These sketches reflect my most ostentatious design intentions, not what the building will actually look like. In the words of Prof. Niland, "you don't know what you don't want to do until you see it."

Limit Sketch 1

This sketch reflects the transparency necessary for positive community interaction. A wall of glass allows abundant natural light, as well as views out. This sketch also echoes the ideas of orientation presented by the participants at Public Meeting 2 by forcing the major view out toward Main Street. The glass wall covers a portion of the existing building demonstrating the symbiotic relationship that the new has with the old.

Limit Sketch 2

Derived from a comment at PM2, the addition caps the building as a provocative and highly non-contextual form. One participant asked, perhaps facetiously, why the addition could not be on top of the existing building. In this case, the addition takes the form of a steel hat that gives the building an entirely new character. The addition is highly non-contextual, both in form and cladding.

Limit Sketch 3

The height of the red block is limited by the existing building to imply their equal weight in the completed building scheme. The misshapen pieces forming the cladding of the block represent the various interests of the community, but their uniform color represents the common interest of its improvement and stability. The tall, central element provides a separation between the large building elements a new at-grade entrance for the building, and a potential "billboard" elevation on both sides of the long element. These faces could be used as physical markers for the building: invitations for further exploration.